

PROBONO

D7.3 Overall LL Implementation Plan and Management (III) - Periodic Monitoring Report & assessment

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DEFINITIONS

A Green Building (GB) (new or retrofit) is a building that, in its design, construction and operation, reduces or eliminates negative impacts, and can create positive impacts, on the climate, social, and natural environment. GBs preserve precious natural resources and improve quality of life. Specifically, this means that GBs should be very energy efficient, use extensively the potential of locally available renewable energy, use sustainable materials, and aim for a low environmental impact over the entire life cycle. GBs offer their users and residents a healthy climate and a high quality of stay, they are resilient e.g., to environmental change and contribute to social inclusion.

Green Neighbourhoods aligned with the European Green Deal¹, is a set of buildings over a delimited area, at a scale that is smaller than a district, with potential synergies, in particular in energy. A green neighbourhood is a neighbourhood that allows for environmentally friendly, sustainable patterns and behaviours to flourish e.g., bioclimatic architecture, renewable energy, soft and zero-emission mobility etc. Green neighbourhoods are the building blocks of Positive Energy Districts (PEDs)² by implementing key elements of PED energy systems. For example, the exchange of energy between buildings increases the share of local self-supply with climate-neutral energy and system efficiency. They also provide the technical conditions to enable Citizen Energy Communities³ and Renewable Energy Communities⁴ to be implemented.

Green Buildings and Neighbourhoods (GBN) in PROBONO are GBs integrated at delimited area or district level with green energy and green mobility management and appropriate infrastructure supported by policies, investments and stakeholders' engagement and behaviours that ensures just transition that maximise the economic and social co-benefits considering a district profile (population size, socio-economic structure, and geographical and climate characteristics). Delivered in the right way, GBN infrastructure is a key enabler of inclusive growth, can improve the accessibility of housing and amenities, reduce poverty and inequality, widen access to jobs and education, make communities more resilient to climate change, and promote public health and wellbeing.

DGNB certification serves as a quality stamp ensuring the state of the building for buyers. The Green Building Council Denmark (2010) established the German certification DGNB meaning 'German Society for Sustainable Buildings'. The Danish version of DGNB was created to obtain a common definition of what sustainability is towards and making it measurable. A consortium of experts was established from all parts of the construction sector. DGNB had to be reshaped for the Danish standards, practice, traditions, and laws but is now available to certify any construction project. DGNB focuses on sustainability and not just the environment, creating a standardised framework for the construction operations conditions and a common language which facilitates communication between professions and helps organize and prioritize the efforts in long and complicated development phases.

Life cycle assessment (LCA)⁵ is a tool used for the systematic quantitative assessment of each material used, energy flows and environmental impacts of products or processes. LCA assesses various aspects associated with development of a product and its potential impact throughout a product's life (i.e., cradle to grave) from raw material acquisition, processing, manufacturing, use and finally its disposal. In PROBONO, LCA represents the statement of a building's total energy, resource consumption and environmental impact in the manufacture, transport, and replacement of materials and for its operation over its expected life. Social life cycle assessment (S-LCA)⁶ is a method to assess the social and sociological aspects of products, their actual and potential positive as well as negative impacts along the life cycle. Life-cycle costing (LCC)⁷ considers all the costs incurred during the lifetime of the product, work, or service.

¹ European_Green_Deal_EN_200710_fin

² SET-Plan Action 3.2: https://setis.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-04/setplan_smartcities_implementationplan.pdf

³ Internal Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944 5 Renewable Energy Directive (EU)

⁴ Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/20012018/2001

⁵ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/16cd2d1d-2216-11e8-ac73-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁶ <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/starting-life-cycle-thinking/life-cycle-approaches/social-lca/>

⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/lcc.htm>

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
BAPV	Building-Applied Photovoltaics
BIPV	Building-Integrated Photovoltaics
BIM	Building Information Modeling
CA	Consortium Agreement
DHC	District Heating and Cooling
DoA	Description of Action (annex I of the Grant Agreement)
DT	Digital Twin
EC	European Commission
EMS	Energy Management System
EPD	Environmental Product Declaration
EV	Electric Vehicle
GA	Grant Agreement
GBN	Green Building Neighbourhood
GIS	Geographic Information System
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
IAQ	Indoor Air Quality
IEQ	Indoor Environmental Quality
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Cost
LL	Living Lab
M&V	Measurement and Verification
NBS	Nature-Based Solutions
NZEB	Near Zero Energy Building
PCM	Phase Change Materials
PC	Project Coordinator
PMC	Project Management Committee
PO	Project Officer
PS	Project Secretariat

Acronym	Description
PV	Photovoltaic
QM	Quality Management
REC	Renewable Energy Community
ROI	Return on Investment
S2V	Solar-to-Vehicle
SC	Scientific Coordinator
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
TMT	Technical Management Team
TL	Task Leader
ToC	Table of Contents
V2B	Vehicle-to-Building
V2G	Vehicle-to-Grid
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive summary

This deliverable, “D7.3 Overall LL Implementation Plan and Management (III)”, provides an in-depth presentation and assessment of PROBONO's Living Labs implementation and monitoring activities as of December 2024 (M36). Progressing upon the foundations established in Task T7.1 during the first reporting period, in collaboration with WP6, and reported in D7.1 and D7.2, the work performed during this period demonstrates significant progress as regards the finalisation of the innovations selection process for all Living Labs, and in the active and agile deployment of innovative solutions across all six Living Labs, with some of the installations to already have transitioned to the operations and use phase, in the way of achieving their targets towards the Green Building Neighbourhood (GBN) framework.

A key achievement during this reporting period in the context of T7.1, has been the development and refinement of a robust monitoring methodology based on an extended ArchiMate (<https://pubs.opengroup.org/architecture/archimate32-doc.singlepage/>) framework. The introduction of this approach, and within the context of the overall Technical Management of PROBONO, has assisted to effectively handle the complexity PROBONO delivery schedule of the selected solutions, further mapped in WP9 as key Exploitable Results (KER) and profiled in WP6 with respect to their impact creating potential, across the six (6) Living Labs while maintaining clear alignment with PROBONO's strategic objectives. Further, the use of the LLs monitoring approach developed by the technical management and applied within T7.1, enables the consistent tracking of innovations, seamless integration with WP6's monitoring process, and the clear mapping of relationships between technologies, stakeholders, and outcomes.

The Living Labs have reached different maturity levels, having finalized their technology selections and produced detailed project plans for all innovations developments. The flagship Living Labs in Dublin and Madrid demonstrate comprehensive integration of technologies across multiple domains, while Porto, Brussels, Aarhus, and Prague showcase specialized excellence in specific areas such as renewable energy, mobility solutions, and human-centred design.

This report outlines specific Living Lab information crucial for PROBONO's exploitation, replication, and sustainability strategy, including detailed plans for technologies deployment, and each Living Lab's contribution to the GBN concept aligning to ISO standards, also delivering an illustrative and complete map of the innovations deployment and their relevance and potential to achieve expected impacts, introducing all implementation requirements for the

selected Digital Twin use cases, highlighting local constraints, and data collection strategies for future adaptation.

A key decision of the monitoring approach within T7.1 has been to be fully aligned with WP6's evaluation framework, utilizing standardized KPIs and measurement processes. This alignment ensures consistent assessment of impacts across construction and operational phases. Furthermore, the application of the GBN framework analysis of WP1 within the Living Labs context, and the mapping of the Living Labs GBN target plan towards mapping the Impacts framework and PROBONO's deployed innovations, aligning them to guidelines and recommendations of standardization bodies improves the project's overall potential for active contribution to international standards through WP9, particularly to ISO 37100 for sustainable communities. Through the Living Labs change management process, WP7 addresses technical challenges that introduce risks, i.e. dependency on external large infrastructure projects in living labs areas, regulatory requirements and permits, performing frequent comprehensive risk assessments for technology deployments for each Living Lab, taking mitigation actions.

The detailed analysis, mapping and monitoring of the innovation deployment at two levels, the Overall Technical Management, and the WP6 and WP7, monitoring functions of which T7.1 is a key contributor, collectively support the goal of PROBONO for transferable outcomes that will enhance the transition capabilities of local communities toward sustainable urban development.

This third iteration of the Living Labs implementation plan represents a crucial milestone in PROBONO's progress, providing both a detailed status update and a clear pathway for the remaining project duration.

1 Introduction

1.1 Mapping PROBONO Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map PROBONO's GA commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
SubTask 7.1.2 – Living Labs Implementation Monitoring	ST7.1.3. Living Labs Implementation monitoring. Perform LL monitoring:		This report provides a 360° view of the Living Labs innovation solutions implementations, applying a model-based methodology based on ArchiMate 3.2. The approach links Objectives, Strategies, Technologies and Services, with the implementation layer as presented in section 2.
	(a) Implement and deploy a monitoring system,	Section 2	
	(b) develop the executive plans following all previous constraints,	Section 3	The monitoring system in WP7 is fully aligned with WP6 monitoring and evaluation framework, based on the Innovation installations definitions in the LLs in WP6 and the KPIs as presented in Section 3.
	(c) identify possible limitations of the technologies and innovations to optimize their performances,	Section 3	
	(d) monitor compliance with existing National and European regulations and policies.	Section 4	Technologies are properly mapped and analyzed based on the developed WP9 analysis of the ERs. Analysis of limitations and risks is provided within each technology presentation in the Risks section and in the Change Management plan of the LLs in section 3. An analysis is provided in section 4 as regards the interplay with WP1 and WP9 aligning towards standardization, a preliminary analysis was performed for all LL Initiatives in their installation of solutions plan.
DELIVERABLE			
D7.3: Overall LL Implementation Plan and Management (III)			
This report formulates the findings of T7.1 and explores step/s C) Periodic Monitoring Report & assessment.			

Table 1: Adherence to PROBONO's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

1.2 Purpose and scope of the document

Deliverable D7.3, the third output of Task 7.1, offers a comprehensive overview of how the Living Labs initiatives align with the overarching goals and objectives of PROBONO. This deliverable builds on the implementation activities of the Living Labs, which are also monitored by WP6, particularly in terms of impact assessment. D7.3 outlines the design, implementation, and deployment plans for the Living Labs, as well as the refined monitoring system developed under

WP7. It also provides valuable insights into the evaluation of technology deployments. Each Living Lab is now advancing toward the construction and operational phases, with fully detailed execution plans in place. For every Living Lab, a thorough mapping of technologies, associated impacts, and key performance indicators (KPIs) has been completed in WP6, and this has been transparently incorporated as a key element of the developed holistic methodology for the LLs monitoring. Additionally, each Living Lab has identified potential issues through risk management processes, and all necessary corrective actions have been documented as changes. These changes are addressed in the corresponding Change Management sections of this document, specific to each Living Lab. Regarding compliance with national and European regulations and policies, this falls under the scope of WP9. Here, the Global Broadband Network (GBN) concept is projected and analysed in collaboration with WP1, based on the ISO 37100 standard.

1.3 Structure of the document and its relationship with other work-packages and deliverables

1.3.1 The document is structured as follows:

- **Section 1:** Introduction – This section provides the context and mapping of the content to PROBONO outputs, relates the work with WPs and explains the relevance to the GBN concept.
- **Section 2:** Living Labs Planning, Management, and Monitoring Approach – Details the methodology for monitoring, evaluating, and managing the Living Labs, including refinements and alignment with project strategies.
- **Section 3:** Living Labs Monitoring – Presents the progress and activities of each Living Lab (Dublin, Madrid, Porto, Brussels, Aarhus, and Prague), covering technologies deployed, stakeholder engagement, and implementation status.
- **Section 4:** Living Labs Projects Consolidation and Analysis – Provides a comparative assessment of applied technologies and strategies across the Living Labs, highlighting replicability potential and alignment to standards.
- **Section 5:** Conclusions – Summarizes key findings, challenges, and next steps for the implementation and management of the Living Labs.

1.3.2 Relationship with Other Work Packages and Deliverables

This deliverable is the third deliverable of Task T7.1, and within the scope of ST7.1.3 that focuses on implementation, monitoring and (re)planning, if necessary, of the PROBONO Living Labs (LLs). The task links to previous reports of the same task (D7.1 and D7.2) and the same work package (the Living Labs M24 deliverables D7.6 Dublin, D7.9 Madrid, D7.12 Porto, D7.15 Brussels, D7.18 Aarhus, and D7.21 Prague) also getting input from Task T5.1 and D5.1 for the Living Labs use cases, and aligns with other work packages (WP1, WP6 and WP9) and deliverables D1.4, D1.11, D6.1, D6.2, D6.3, D6.4, D9.3, D9.7, and D9.8. Also, this deliverable, relates to all work relevant to the GBN technologies and solutions and methods implemented by WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5, and integrates and monitors their installations schedule and deployment and testing plan of these in the Living Labs.

1.4 Relevance to the GBN concept

PROBONO project envisions the Living Labs (LLs) as the testbed for all Green Buildings and Neighbourhoods (GBN) innovations which are developed in WP2 to WP5, to help form strategies leading to the realization of the GBN framework concepts that are formalised in WP1, delivering energy-efficient, climate-resilient, and socially inclusive solutions. Each Living Lab serves as a hub for experimentation, where sustainable energy solutions, advanced digital tools, resource-efficient materials are tested and refined. The overarching objectives of PROBONO tested in the Living Labs can be categorized into the following key impact clusters:

Optimizing Resource Efficiency and the Building Lifecycle: PROBONO develops innovations for the efficient use of materials towards reducing embodied energy, leading the way in sustainable construction materials and upcycling, facilitating renovation strategies that minimize waste and reduce the environmental footprint of buildings. Further, the employment of phase change materials (PCM), smart metering, and solar-to-vehicle integration, ensure that energy storage and management are both cost-effective and space-efficient.

Advancing Energy Performance and Sustainability: At the core of the PROBONO Living Labs is the ambition to result solutions that will impact on energy efficiency and sustainability for GBNs. PROBONO pioneers a suite of renewable energy technologies, integrating hybrid green roofs, photovoltaic systems (BAPV and BIPV), second-life battery storage, Digital Twins to optimize energy flows. Similarly, the solutions set explores geothermal energy models embedding renewable energy into district-scale infrastructure of urban environments. Further, PROBONO

provides solutions to advance buildings into near-zero energy consumption exemplars, while promoting energy-efficient renovations.

Innovating Urban Mobility and Energy Systems: As cities evolve, mobility and energy systems are crucial in achieving sustainability. PROBONO pioneers district heating and cooling, leverages renewable energy communities to provide scalable and resilient solutions for urban energy needs, also deploying S2V and V2B technologies, flow battery storage, and integrates mobility solutions into energy networks to show how mobility and energy can be seamlessly connected.

Enhancing Environmental quality and Social Inclusion: The PROBONO Living Labs emphasize in improving indoor environmental quality and promoting behavioural change with citizen engagement programs to encourage citizens adopt sustainable practices via data and information driven insights and learning and technology transfer initiatives, thereby fostering community participation in decisions for smart energy solutions and retrofit strategies, making users active contributors to the energy transition.

Scaling and Replicating Sustainable Innovations, Influencing Policy and Regulatory Frameworks: PROBONO envisions that the developed set of Innovations will ensure transferability, being scalable and flexible for successful replication across Europe. To this end it works towards standardisation so to facilitate the adoption of sustainable energy solutions in other cities and countries. Likewise, in WP5 it creates decision-support tools for architects and engineers, enabling evidence-based sustainability planning in urban design. To ensure long-term impact, the PROBONO project aligns its innovations with European policy and regulatory frameworks and local regulations adaptations, to integrate renovation strategies within the broader framework of the EU Green Deal.

Task 7.1 focuses on establishing methods and tools to monitor the progress of the Living Labs development, ensuring full alignment with the monitoring framework developed in WP6 and adherence to the core driver values and drivers outlined above. The activities of Task 7.1 are closely co-ordinated with the directions and outputs of WP8 and WP9 to maximize the impact of the deployed technology initiatives.

2 Living Labs planning, management and monitoring approach

2.1 Living Labs Methodology Refinement

PROBONO is a visionary and highly complex initiative aimed at creating Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBN), where innovations, technologies, and solutions for materials upcycling and reuse, energy efficiency, digital innovation, and community engagement converge to build sustainable, future-ready cities. The sheer scale and complexity of PROBONO—encompassing an ambitious technology and methods development plan led by a diverse consortium of partners, and the deployment of many cutting-edge technology solutions across six Living Labs (LLs)—demand a robust, structured approach to ensure alignment between strategic goals and on-the-ground implementation.

PROBONO features a rich innovations palette, spanning materials and logistics planning, energy systems and building lifecycles, digitalization, and behavioural changes, all of which involve strong interactions with stakeholders and citizens. With a wide set of technologies, methods, and tools developed across WP1 to WP5 and deployed in PROBONO's Living Labs, the need for a clear, structured, and interconnected framework was paramount. This is where ArchiMate 3.2 (<https://pubs.opengroup.org/architecture/archimate32-doc/>), a powerful and open-source enterprise architecture modelling language, shines.

It must be mentioned that ArchiMate has been extended and adapted with additional semantics to better tell the story of PROBONO and to interconnect important project concepts (Figure 1 is an ArchiMate projection of the “Motivation Layer” concepts of PROBONO, as these appear in the text of the Call). These include Technologies, Exploitable Results (ER), and Impacts, which are linked to PROBONO's goals, drivers, and objectives, and mapped to the innovations deployed in the Living Labs. This extended adaptation of ArchiMate which has been made to be PROBONO tailored, serves as the backbone of PROBONO's planning and execution monitoring, enabling a comprehensive view of the project's architecture and progress, and to address the complexity of a large-scale installation project such as PROBONO, that uses its results to form and establish concepts that are placed within a wider European and International standards context.

To this end, PROBONO's management framework, applied both to the project overall and to the Living Labs, not only models static architectural elements but also captures the interplay of stakeholders, processes, and technology interventions within PROBONO's solutions production

and the Living Labs. This results in a 360-degree visualization of how the project’s outcomes translate into scalable solutions tested in the Living Labs.

Figure 1: PROBONO EU call context

2.2 Living Labs and Impact Management

PROBONO in WP6 defines an LLs evaluation framework based on Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), Measurement and Verification (M&V) plans and Life Cycle (LC) methodologies (reported in D6.1). Impact Management is performed via the monitoring of the KPIs. WP6 sets the baseline calculations for the Living Labs (reported in D6.2), and deploys a monitoring program for Living Lab, based on the Innovations deployment programme of each Living Lab (reported in D6.3).

WP6 performs impact assessment under operational and life cycle perspectives, covering (a) the construction phase, and (b) the operational phase of each Living Lab.

Figure 3 illustrates the KPIs per impact as those relate to the implementation of the technologies

Figure 3: Impacts and KPIs during construction phase for the LLs.

Figure 2: KPIs for Impacts; Construction and Use phases.

in the Living Labs during construction phase, while Figure 2 shows both impacts and KPIs used for LLs Impacts monitoring.

2.3 PROBONO Innovations development and deployment models.

Figure 4: PROBONO Enablers

The PROBONO “Enablers” are the resources and capabilities in ArchiMate terms produced by the innovation development-oriented work packages WP1-WP5. These are shown in Figure 4.

The WP6 monitoring framework has produced a clear mapping of the impacts of each of the resources produced, this analysis is in deliverable D6.1.

Working upon the analysis of D6.1, WP7 monitoring framework produced a complete and fully detailed map of all technologies vs. their impact, Figure 6 shows only the “High” and “Medium” impact technologies per impact category.

Main KPIs associated with the Impact									
[Main KPI 1] Primary Energy Consumption									
Life cycle stages									
Product stage (A1-A3)	Construction stage (A4-A5)		Use (B1-B7)		End of Life (C1-C4)		Beyond the Building Life Cycle (D)		
Living Labs									
Dublin	Madrid	Porto	Aarhus	Prague	Brussels				
Impact assessment associated deliverables					D6.6 and D6.7 Operation D6.8 Final Evaluation				
WP3 innovations expected influence (High; Medium; Low; None)									
a.1	a.2	a.3	a.4	b.1	b.2	b.3	b.4	c.1	c.2
WP4 innovations expected influence (High; Medium; Low; None)									
a.1	a.2	b.1	c.1	c.2	d.1	e.1	e.2	f.1	

Figure 5: Relevance Map of Innovations per KPI.

Figure 6: Impacts and Technology Mapping

2.4 Innovations Mapping.

WP9 works towards defining a clear path for the exploitation, replication and sustainability of the results of PROBONO, by (a) identifying and mapping all project exploitable results (ERs) according to their exploitation potential and characteristics, and (b) accelerating the strategy development of PROBONO’s Living Labs (LLs) formation and evolution to Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBNs), with a particular focus on their long-term sustainability and replicability aspects.

Figure 7: WP2, WP3 and WP4 innovations and their ER mapping.

The framework of innovations developed captures 42 in total results (presented in D9.3).

Figure 7 shows the ArchiMate model of the innovations, their related Task, the Task participants, the Exploitable Result record (ER_ID), and the corresponding exploitation leader per result.

Certainly, these innovations which are part of the PROBONO portfolio of solutions are being developed via innovation related initiatives in the Living Labs of PROBONO.

To monitor this activity, a thorough analysis has been performed in WP6 (D6.4) where for every living lab, monitored activities have been identified (obtaining an activity record, e.g. “D1” is the

Dublin Hybrid Green roof initiative (sub) project. In WP7, this approach has been harmoniously aligned, so, in the developed monitoring framework, all activities have been mapped using the same ID and naming approach, so to be consistent across all PROBONO activities.

Figure 8: Mapping of WP6 monitoring approach to WP7 LL initiatives.

Figure 8 shows this mapping, where the Gantt chart of all LL1 – Dublin activities, is using the same names and IDs for the innovation actions. The ArchiMate view links the Living Labs locations, with the projects, the deployed technologies and the leading partners responsible for these technologies’ development.

Figure 9: Innovations deployment in Living Labs.

Figure 9 illustrates how the model supports all concepts interconnections, linking the various concepts to specific and tangible PROBONO artefacts. The innovations deployment in the Living Labs provides a view connecting all Monitored Initiatives, with the responsible and leading partner of each innovation. The innovations as presented in the exploitation management context of WP9, are mapped to the produced assets and resources in the technology and innovation creation work packages and their tasks resulting “assets”, of which there is also a clear mapping in WP6. In sequence, these are further mapped to the Impacts and the corresponding KPIs, while the Impacts depicted are the ones that have “High” and “Strong” relevance.

2.5 Living Labs Project Managements and monitoring

The PROBONO underlying management model, which has been developed in ArchiMate and is being discussed in this section, integrates all the corresponding Implementation layer definitions, for all the project and specifically for Task 7.1, via the model, all the contractual but

Figure 10: Task 7.1 Project Management ArchiMate view

also the project generated outputs are being defined, as this is a dynamic process following the progress of PROBONO’s developments.

2.7 Methodology Value points.

The PROBONO implementation adapts the ArchiMate methodology framework resulting a management approach supported by a freely available and capable tool (<https://www.archimatetool.com>), in the task to manage the large complexities introduced across the considerable number of innovation developments (WP9 identifies 42 exploitable results), which are deployed upon six (6) Living Labs. The extensions introduced accommodate PROBONO's specific architecture requirements, establishing standardized protocols for implementation, monitoring, and performance assessment. The resulting approach delivers five key technical outcomes:

Living Lab Management: The framework implements structured mapping of operational dependencies, stakeholder interfaces, and technology deployment vectors. Integration with WP6 monitoring protocols enables systematic KPI tracking and verification procedures.

Consistent referencing of project components across WPs: ArchiMate monitors the systematic deployment of WP1-WP5 innovations across the WP7 Living Labs, adopting a standardized identification for innovation tracking as postulated in WP6. Further, the framework facilitates and integrates the definitions of WP9 Exploitable Results (ERs). Hence, it establishes a unified technical vocabulary and standardized information capture, and recorded across work all packages. This harmonization ensures consistent classification of technologies, methodologies, and KPIs, enabling efficient cross-referencing and integration of deliverables between work packages. A Knowledge Graph implementation maps system dependencies, enabling dynamic adaptation of project governance protocols.

Enhancement of the multi-factor Impacts analysis and KPIs Framework: PROBONO manages a highly complex performance tracking process across 10 distinct impact categories each of which is linked to more than one innovation across 6 Living Labs. This becomes a challenge due to interdependencies between innovation deployments, varying implementation timelines, and real-time performance feedback loops across Living Labs. Further, with this approach is completely clear and transparent the role of each stakeholder, which is especially critical for the proper assessment of the technologies. This helps engage the appropriate resources when for example an indicator requires to be computed, in terms of laying down the facts of all parties involved for data collection to KPI calculation.

3 Living Labs Monitoring

3.1 LL1 Dublin

Dublin LL timeplan		2024												2025												2026												Start-End	
Partner	Major LL activities	Q1			Q2			Q3			Q4			Q1			Q2			Q3			Q4																
		25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60		
SOP	D1-Hybrid Green Roof																																					25	60
	<i>Planning, tendering and Consultation</i>																																					25	36
	<i>Finalisation and planning permission</i>																																					37	42
	<i>Installation</i>																																					43	48
	<i>Monitoring, Public unveiling</i>																																					49	54
	<i>Review</i>																																					55	60
FRHF	D2-Photovoltaic system (BAPV)																																					25	60
	<i>Planning, tendering and Consultation</i>																																					25	33
	<i>Ballast and Frame Installation</i>																																					34	39
	<i>Panel Installation</i>																																					40	42
	<i>Cabling</i>																																					43	48
	<i>Monitoring, EMS integration, Public unveiling</i>																																					49	54
	<i>Review</i>																																					55	60
FRHF	D3-Photovoltaic system (BIPV)																																					25	60
	<i>Planning, tendering and Consultation</i>																																					25	36
	<i>Finalisation and planning permission</i>																																					37	42
	<i>Panel Installation</i>																																					43	45
	<i>Cabling</i>																																					46	48
	<i>Monitoring, EMS integration, Public unveiling</i>																																					49	54
	<i>Review</i>																																					55	60
BEE	D4-Battery bank																																					25	60
	<i>Planning, Consultation Location and Function</i>																																					25	39
	<i>Installation</i>																																					40	42
	<i>Cabling</i>																																					43	45
	<i>Monitoring EMS and IT integration</i>																																					46	48
	<i>Monitoring</i>																																					49	60
CIDAUT	D5-2 Way EV chargers																																					25	60
	<i>Planning and Fleet Consultation</i>																																					25	36
	<i>Installation</i>																																					37	39
	<i>Monitoring, EMS and IT Integration</i>																																					40	48
	<i>Monitoring</i>																																					49	57
	<i>Review</i>																																					58	60
BOVLABS	D6-Energy trading platform																																					25	60
	<i>Planning and system requirements</i>																																					25	36
	<i>Implementation and technology integration</i>																																					37	48
	<i>monitoring & staff dashboard creation</i>																																					49	60
AKKA	D7-DT																																					25	60
	<i>Development</i>																																					25	36
	<i>Configuration</i>																																					33	39
	<i>Deployment and Testing</i>																																					40	54
	<i>Review</i>																																					55	60
STAM	D8-Insulation																																					25	60
	<i>Monitoring and Public Dissemination</i>																																					25	36
	<i>Review</i>																																					37	60
SIN	D9-Social Innovations																																					25	60
	<i>Configuration of actions and setup</i>																																					25	51
	<i>Public Engagement</i>																																					25	54
	<i>Review</i>																																					25	60

Figure 12: Dublin LL Gantt Chart, M25 - M60

3.1.1 Dublin LL Technologies Deployment

The Dublin Living Lab (LL1) integrates sustainable technologies into urban environments, focusing on energy efficiency, renewable energy adoption, and community engagement. Situated in Dún Laoghaire, the Living Lab features key interventions such as hybrid green roofs, photovoltaic (BAPV) systems, Building Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV), second-life battery storage, bi-directional EV chargers, an Energy Management System (EMS) and a DT for decision-making. It also emphasizes retrofitting heritage buildings with innovative insulation solutions, balancing modern energy goals with conservation efforts. Social innovations, such as GeoDesign workshops and retrofit Post-Occupancy Evaluations (POE), ensure the active involvement of local communities in shaping sustainable urban practices. The Gantt Chart of LL1 is shown in Figure 12, the innovations listed in the Gantt are the subject of the following paragraphs within this section.

3.1.1.1 D1 – Hybrid Green Roof

This initiative emphasizes the dual benefits of biodiversity enhancement and stormwater runoff mitigation, addressing key sustainability goals. The implementation requirements for the hybrid green roof involve placing a new root-resistant membrane over the existing roof membrane and greening it, with the vegetation serving as ballast for solar panels. A survey of the current state of the County Hall roof infrastructure identified that while the roof is capable of load bearing, it requires refurbishment and waterproofing. Regarding the consultation process, local authorities in Ireland do not require planning permission for works on their property, but a public consultation process is typically necessary. For assembly requirements, access to the roof will be granted, while local constraints include the building's protected status, which restricts interventions to the rooftop of the newer extension, as the old rooftop cannot be used due to design differences.

The implementation of the green roof alongside the BAPV has been analysed. A limitation in the approach was that while a green roof might improve biodiversity, economically, it would extend the ROI period by approximately one-third, as the available space for solar panels would have to be reduced. However, the green roof with a photovoltaic (PV) array has been approved for implementation, leveraging cost savings from the dual-layer membrane refurbishment, which involved installing a new membrane over the existing one, and insulation. The green roof elements will serve as ballast for the solar panels, enhancing stability and reducing additional material requirements. Hence, despite the extended return on investment (ROI) period due to

the reduced space for solar panels, the decision aligns with the Council's commitment to lead by example, fostering broader adoption of sustainable practices among external stakeholders. Last, the benefit of limiting stormwater runoff does not appear to be quite impactful. Since the building is very close to the sea, it does not place significant pressure on the combined sewer system. However, the concerns regarding waterlogging have been mitigated by limiting the green coverage to partial roof areas, ensuring efficient drainage without additional significant expenditures on new infrastructure.

Risks: Risks include Weather-related wear due to proximity to the sea and challenges in balancing biodiversity benefits with reduced solar panel space could extend ROI. Additionally, waterlogging risks and maintenance demands might pose long-term operational challenges, however, these have been addressed through, e.g., the partial green coverage to manage water efficiently while maintaining biodiversity benefits.

3.1.1.2 D2 – Photovoltaic System (BAPV)

The installation of a BAPV solar array at County Hall aligns with PROBONO's 'Integrator-Centric' approach. This implementation will require the close cooperation between complementary projects and partners, including Centrica, the 'Energy Performance Contractor', EU Project DeliveREE (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101032833/reporting>) and Codema (<https://www.codema.ie>)

The BAPV technology is promising, as for a configuration of 650m² BAPV solar array on the roof of County Hall (Figure 13), with an estimated cost of around €200,000, the installation is expected to generate up to 161 MWh annually and at minimum ca. 80 MWh. While the projected energy generation is significant for a BAPV system, it must be noted that the building's current baseline consumption stands at 1500MWh

Figure 13: County Hall Roof

annually. While the BAPV (Building-Applied Photovoltaics) is projected to cover approximately 5.6% to 10.7% of the total energy consumption, this coverage is expected to evolve as the building's energy footprint increases. However, the integration of PV systems and heat exchangers will significantly reduce on-site fossil fuel consumption, accelerating the building's decarbonization. Leveraging the decreasing carbon intensity of the grid and eliminating reliance

on gas boilers, the intervention aligns with long-term sustainability goals for a cleaner and more energy-efficient future.

Risks: Uncertainties in budgeting and tendering processes pose risks, potentially impacting timelines. Risks also include potential structural and installation challenges on the existing roof infrastructure, which may incur unforeseen costs. Limited energy generation compared to the building's consumption baseline could affect impact, as energy demand is projected to rise. Coordination risks also exist due to the need for close collaboration among multiple partners and projects.

3.1.1.3 D3 - Photovoltaic system (BIPV)

The Building Integrated Photovoltaic (BIPV) systems technology installation will support renewable energy adoption, reduce emissions, and promote sustainability goals across the GBN initiative. The BIPV initiative focuses on generating renewable energy while integrating seamlessly with building facades. The installations at County Hall and the Lexlcon Library aim to demonstrate the viability and scalability of BIPV technology in urban environments (Table 2 shows the energy profile of the BIPV interventions in LL1).

Intervention	Output in MWh/a	Baseload covered for building/a
County Hall Roof	161	5.6-10.7%
County Hall South	13.1	2.135%
County Hall West	5.1	3.9%
Lexlcon South	21	21.7%
Lexlcon West	6.6	10.56%

Table 2: BIPV interventions energy profile

Lexicon Library: The Lexicon Library is set to host multiple BIPV systems across its facades, with the West-South-West and Western facades being the primary sites for installations: (a) the West-South-West Facade installation will cover 150m² (Figure 15), producing approximately 21,000 kWh annually. The PV system will operate with a generator output of 40 kWp, achieving a performance ratio of 91.21%, with grid export maintained at 21,000k Wh/year, including module degradation. (b) Western Facade is a larger yet less sunny installation covering 130m² will generate approximately 6,600 kWh annually (Figure 14). These installations, together with a smaller decorative intervention incorporating the DLR logo, aim to generate a total of 27,000

Figure 15: Lexicon Library South Façade

Figure 14: Lexicon Library West Façade

kWh annually. This production surpasses the library's fossil fuel-based energy consumption, positioning the Lexicon Library on a clear path toward carbon neutrality. As energy upgrades reduce baseline consumption, the share of renewable energy supplied by BIPV will rise, further advancing decarbonization efforts for the Dublin LL's GBN hub.

County Hall: At County Hall, BIPV systems are planned for the southern and western facades:

(a) Southern Façade covers 40m² (see Figure 16), this installation will generate 13,100 kWh annually, (b) Western Façade has a capacity of 95m² (see Figure 17), it will produce 5,100 kWh annually. Combined, these installations will contribute to renewable energy generation and address approximately 10% of County Hall's 2030 emissions reduction targets.

Figure 16: Country Hall South Wall

Further, the Dublin LL will compare the performance of Building Attached Photovoltaic (BAPV) and BIPV systems at a separate Dún Laoghaire-Rathdown County Council site. This research, conducted by Solar Evolution, will provide critical insights into the efficiency of these systems while serving as a public demonstration of renewable energy technology. Solar Evolution will also act as regulatory consultants for Fraunhofer and the PROBONO project, assisting in disseminating awareness of the initiative.

Figure 17: Country Hall West Wall

Permits: The Building Integrated PV would require Part 8 planning permission; this typically takes 4-6 months to process and receive a decision. As soon as the final budget is clear, the process will be activated.

Risks: Delays in planning permission and tendering, especially for installations on protected structures like the Lexicon Library. High costs and shading issues in certain areas may limit energy output, impacting financial feasibility. Challenges in public awareness and acceptance might also hinder the technology's broader adoption.

3.1.1.4 D4 - Battery Bank

The Battery Bank initiative at the Dublin Living Lab is an integral part of its Green Building Neighbourhood (GBN) strategy, designed to enhance energy efficiency and sustainability. It supports the concepts of energy trading, optimizing renewable energy usage, and contributes to carbon neutrality goals. It involves the installation of a 145-kWh battery bank (which could change to a higher capacity) constructed from *second-life lithium-ion batteries* sourced from electric vehicles and emphasizes reuse of materials to reduce environmental impact and circular economy. However, capacity is likely to be changed, as smaller units are currently being considered. These are self-contained, helping reduce the risk of fire due to built-in fire mitigation measures

Technical Specifications and Functionality: The battery bank will store excess energy generated by the Building Integrated Photo Voltaic (BIPV) systems during periods of low demand, such as weekends and holidays. It will then release this energy during peak times to optimize energy

usage, reduce costs, and ensure operational continuity. Key features include: (a) Capacity: 145 kWh, with a 2-hour full charge time using the appropriate cabling, (b) Operational Role: Provides backup power for County Hall, supports grid interaction by storing low-cost off-peak electricity, and feeds energy back into the building during high-demand periods. The overall system solution will be employing: (a) self-contained modular units and a larger centralized battery bank, to ensure flexibility, scalability, and operational resilience. The self-contained modular units will be smaller, independently operating systems designed to provide localized energy storage and backup power, offering redundancy and reducing reliance on a single energy storage source. They are ideal for short-term energy needs and can respond quickly to localized demand fluctuations or emergencies. The larger centralized battery bank will handle bulk energy storage and grid interaction.

Infrastructure and Requirements: The smaller units don't need additional fire suppression and can be installed immediately in the basement. The larger centralised battery bank will be housed in a fire-resistant and weatherproof container provided by BEE, ensuring safety and durability. The container will be insulated with materials like rock wool, maintaining an internal temperature between 10°C and 30°C. Ventilation, fire detection, and extinguishing systems are mandatory to mitigate risks. Potential installation locations for the centralised battery bank include: (a) Dún Laoghaire Harbour, preferred for its safety and existing cabling infrastructure, minimizing the need for additional civil engineering works, (b) Behind the Pavilion Theatre, which would require significant additional expenditure for cabling and structural adjustments, and (c) County Hall Basement, which is deemed unsuitable due to fire safety concerns.

Risks: The primary challenge for the battery bank is fire safety, particularly in proximity to staff and public areas. To address this, the Dún Laoghaire Harbour location has been prioritized, reducing potential risks and increasing public accessibility. Also, the additional costs for the container.

3.1.1.1.5 D5 – 2 Way EV Chargers

The two-way electric vehicle (EV) charging system is a key component of its mobility and sustainability strategy, enabling bi-directional charging for energy optimization and carbon footprint reduction. This infrastructure will leverage the County Hall basement Mobility Hub as a central location for the installation (see Figure 18). The chargers will contribute to decarbonization by leveraging renewable energy sources when available, storing surplus energy from photovoltaic systems, and supporting off-peak energy consumption patterns. This will maximize the utilization of the EV fleet's energy capacity, enhancing the overall efficiency of the Dublin LL energy network. Two of these units will be installed.

Figure 18: Country Hall Mobility Hub, 2-way EV Charging

Technical Features: The bi-directional chargers feature Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) functionality, allowing energy stored in EV batteries to be fed back into the grid during peak demand periods. This capability supports energy trading and enhances energy management flexibility. The system will be implemented via CHAdeMO and CCS2-compatible chargers provided by CIDAUT, with two proposed models (a) CHAdeMO-only charger, (b) Dual CHAdeMO and CCS2 charger, offering greater compatibility for current and future fleet requirements.

Energy Management Integration: The charging system will be connected to an Energy Management System (EMS) developed by BOVLABS. This software will provide real-time monitoring and data analytics, enabling features such as (a) Session management and billing, (b) Predictive charging algorithms that optimize grid flexibility, (c) Integration with the Digital Twin for advanced decision-making and data visualization. The EMS will rely on Open Charge Point Protocol (OCPP) standards to ensure interoperability with other systems and facilitate peer-to-peer energy trading.

Risks: The primary risk involves ensuring compatibility with a growing variety of EV models in the fleet. To mitigate this, the project prioritizes dual-compatible chargers and allocates a flexible budget with contingency measures to address cost overruns. CIDAUT has committed to covering potential budgetary gaps to ensure seamless implementation. An additional risk is the current makeup of the fleet, as only two vehicles are currently V2X compatible, limiting the scope of this initiative.

3.1.1.6 D6 – Energy Trading Platform

The Energy Trading Platform developed by BOVLABS, advances sustainability by reducing carbon emissions through prioritization of renewable energy, as it maximizes the utilization of surplus energy generated by photovoltaic systems by ensuring it is either stored or redistributed efficiently. It supports peer-to-peer energy transactions, enabling decentralized energy management. It is designed to enable automated load balancing and energy trading across various interconnected technologies, including photovoltaics (BAPV and BIPV), battery banks, and EV charging infrastructure.

Technical Features: The Energy Trading Platform integrates multiple technologies and relies on a robust Energy Management System (EMS). Its primary functions include: (a) Real-Time Energy Management, which enables real-time monitoring of energy generation, consumption, and storage across connected systems, (b) Automated Load Balancing, which distributes energy efficiently between the building, EV chargers, and battery banks based on dynamic demand, and (c) Energy Trading, which facilitates Building-to-Vehicle (B2V) and Building-to-Grid (B2G) transactions, optimizing energy flow to reduce costs and improve grid stability.

The system employs the Open Charge Point Protocol (OCPP) for seamless communication and interoperability between the charging stations, EMS, and back-end systems. It also includes, (a) Charge Point Management System, with user authentication, session management, billing, and transaction handling, (b) Predictive Analytics, which uses a smart algorithm to predict energy flexibility for 15-minute intervals, optimizing grid use during peak and off-peak hours, and (c) data Integration with the Digital Twin (DT), that provides real-time data to the DT for advanced visualization and decision-making.

Risks: To ensure interoperability among diverse technical systems and to achieve the integration of the Energy Trading Platform with the EMS and DT. Requires collaboration between stakeholders, including DLR Energy Department and Solar Evolution. There are additional risks regarding ownership transfer in the long term.

3.1.1.7 D7 – Digital Twin

The Digital Twin (DT) involves the integration of real-time data that are generated via the energy management and trading initiatives, provides advanced visualization, and the facilitates intelligent decision-making. The Digital Twin enables the dynamic modelling of energy systems, environmental conditions, and user behaviours to optimize the energy efficiency and

sustainability of the Living Lab and empowers stakeholders to monitor, predict, and manage energy usage and building operations in unprecedented ways.

Technical Features: (a) Real-Time Monitoring and Integration, implementing continuous data streams from the building's energy infrastructure, including BIPV systems, EV chargers, battery banks, and energy trading platforms, and integration with Internet of Things (IoT) sensors for indoor air quality (IAQ), thermal comfort, and energy consumption, (b) Dynamic Simulation and 3D visualization of building systems, energy flows, and environmental performance for enhanced stakeholder understanding, with scenario modelling capabilities to predict the impact of design changes, energy storage strategies, or load-balancing interventions, (c) AI-driven analytics to forecast energy demand and optimize grid interactions and recommendations for operational improvements, energy trading opportunities, and user behaviour modifications, (d) Interoperability and Communication, using standardized protocols like BIM and IFC for seamless integration with other technologies, including the Energy Management System (EMS) and Energy Trading Platform, letting to facilitate Building-to-Grid (B2G) and Building-to-Vehicle (B2V) energy transactions, and (e) Stakeholder Engagement and User-Centric Design, providing interactive dashboards for real-time feedback to building managers, energy operators, and occupants facilitating community participation in energy-saving initiatives.

Risks: (a) Interoperability requirements to ensure compatibility with diverse technical systems, including BIPV, EV charging infrastructure, and the Energy Trading Platform and Digital Twin solutions with the IT environment of LL Dublin, (b) Stakeholder collaboration as it integrates developments through many innovations in this LL, and (c) data security and privacy covered through PROBONO data management policies. Additional risks concern the ownership transfer in the long term.

3.1.1.8 D8 – Insulation

Figure 19: Harbour Lodge Ceilings - Insulation

The insulation technology installation at the Dublin LL is about retrofitting buildings of important architectural heritage for energy efficiency while preserving their historical features and significance. The aim of this action is to achieve a Building Energy Rating (BER) of B2 for the Harbour Master's Lodge, providing a replicable model for retrofitting heritage buildings across Dún Laoghaire and similar regions. Interim reports from these tests will inform future insulation technologies and retrofitting projects for climate resilience goals in the direction implementing Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBN). The Harbour Master's Lodge (see Figure 19) serves as the pilot site for testing various insulation materials and methods, showcasing the potential for harmonizing modern energy solutions with heritage conservation.

Technical Solution: The insulation intervention at the Harbour Master's Lodge includes the installation of materials supplied by SOPREMA and Maclyn Conservation Joinery, including: (a) Wood Fibre Insulation (100mm), applied to voids behind radiators and shutter boxes, (b) Hemp Fibre Insulation (100mm), installed in specific voids behind radiators, (c) Blown-In Loose Insulation (1 m³), used in the voids behind internal window heads, and (d) Rockwool Insulation (100 mm) added to targeted areas for improved thermal performance.

The work was conducted under the oversight of Neil Crimmins & Cathal Crimmins Architects and completed by Maclyn Conservation Joinery. Each insulation type is undergoing testing to assess its efficiency in reducing heat transfer. These tests are conducted in collaboration with Dún Laoghaire County Council and University College Dublin (UCD) over a one-year period.

This action has been completed and is currently in the monitoring phase. During an Open House event this summer, 120 members of the public visited the Lodge to inspect the works, also seeking advice regarding retrofitting measures for their own homes. This included a member of a UK county council, wishing to undertake similar works in their Local Authority

Risks: The heritage status of the building imposes strict limitations on permissible interventions. Despite these constraints, the project demonstrates that heritage preservation and climate action can coexist, creating a blueprint for sustainable retrofitting in the private and public sectors.

3.1.1.9 D9 – Social Innovations

The social innovations in the Dublin LL are designed to engage the community, promote inclusivity, and foster long-term sustainable practices. These initiatives include collaborative platforms, educational workshops, and community-centric programs that aim to create awareness and a wide active participation.

GeoDesign Workshops, scheduled for 2025 aim to include stakeholders into the design process, engaging residents, local authorities, and design professionals, to collaboratively plan sustainable urban interventions. The workshops facilitate an inclusive dialogue, ensuring that community voices are heard in shaping the built environment. The initiative will be in collaboration with the University of Naples Plinius Centre and will create a GIS model of the entire decarbonizing zone, as well as 3D models of the PROBONO GBN and two other areas of interest. This will allow for the mapping of climate hazards, and invite both the public and local government to propose and model the effects of mitigation measures

Beaufort Retrofit Post-Occupancy Evaluations, provide insights into user satisfaction and behavioural patterns, focusing on improving indoor environmental quality (IEQ). This evaluation serves as a feedback mechanism to enhance future retrofit strategies while directly engaging occupants in the energy efficiency discourse.

Open House Events: (a) 2024 Event: Focused on displaying insulation interventions, this activity has been completed without any risks reported, (b) 2025 Event: Planned to showcase

interventions and technologies. Preparations are ongoing, with potential delays anticipated in its implementation.

CERNA Survey: A survey facilitated by SIN to gather insights related to the LL.

Risk: Cost identified as a risk factor requiring prioritisation of foreseen activities.

3.1.2 Dublin Living Lab Change Management

The Dublin Living Lab has revised its implementation plan to expand the scope of renewable energy interventions and address challenges related to heritage buildings, ensuring alignment with the project's goals and sustainability objectives.

The implementation of Building-Integrated and Building-Applied Photovoltaic (BIPV and BAPV) systems will be expanded to cover a larger surface area on two historic public buildings, County Hall and Lexicon South. This adjustment addresses an underestimation in the initial proposal regarding the total surface area and budget required for these systems. The expanded implementation will enhance the energy performance of these flagship buildings, contributing to achieving NZEB performance improvements and significant reductions in greenhouse gas emissions.

Dublin has prioritized these renewable energy technologies to achieve energy and sustainability KPIs within the Living Lab scenario. Implementation is scheduled to begin in 2025, with energy production expected to reduce dependency on non-renewable energy sources for the targeted buildings. The intervention will also enhance the visibility of EU-funded initiatives due to the prominence of the Lexicon Building in the city. The Dublin City Council has decided to reallocate funds initially planned for a battery bank installation to further support the BIPV implementation. This decision was driven by significant fire safety concerns and the complexities of deploying battery technology in heritage buildings. Redirecting these resources ensures a more effective and impactful renewable energy intervention.

3.1.3 Dublin LL methodology-based mapping

Figure 20: ArchiMate Schematic Diagram of Dublin LL

3.1.3.1 Innovations Mapping and KPIs

The ArchiMate schematic of Figure 20 shows an overall view of the innovations, the related locations of their testing and the main facilitators of those innovations, as described in section 3.1.1.

Each innovation installation and testing activity in the Living Lab is linked with the main stakeholder (e.g. SOP), the location (e.g. LL1-Country Hall / Roof), and the related asset which is the output of the work of an innovation related WP (e.g. 3a6.Evaporative Green Roof). The diagram also provides information about the related PROBONO Milestone where each innovation installation is expected to be completed.

Behind all those artifacts which have been given semantic meaning according to Archimate methodology, there is a complete model, which connects the different semantic element levels of the methodology, i.e. Motivation, Strategy, Business, Application, Technology and

Figure 21: Dublin LL Locations and interventions

Implementation and Migration layers).

Figure 21 is a map projection of the interventions and their related locations within the Living Lab.

Figure 22 shows the list of KPIs that LL Dublin (LL1) will be monitoring, in collaboration with WP6 (see Deliverable D6.x, and specifically D6.4).

Figure 22: Dublin Related KPIs and linked innovations.

3.1.3.2 Dublin LL Use cases and Data

Figure 23: Dublin LL Use Cases

Figure 24: Dublin Use Cases Datasets

3.1.3.3

The Dublin Living Lab use cases (Figure 23 shows the top-level use cases diagram, and Figure 24 shows the datasets related to those use cases as identified in task T5.1), are centred around four key high-level areas, each addressing critical aspects of urban and environmental management in the context of the Living Lab.

A. Environmental Condition System: The primary goal of the Environmental Condition System is to gather and manage environmental data, both internal and external to physical structures, throughout their lifecycle. This system leverages sensors and other sources to deliver meaningful insights and analytics for stakeholders. By understanding inhabitants' behaviour in different environmental conditions, both internal and external, this system enables better control and decision-making. Internal data is collected through sensors installed within the building, while external data, such as weather information, is sourced from external services and devices. A secondary emphasis within this system is on efficient waste management. Recycling is a mandatory requirement, and a dedicated use case focuses on managing recycling data, including the volumes and weights of various waste types. Facility managers benefit from this comprehensive system, which supports data-driven decision-making and helps mitigate environmental impacts.

Use Cases: Monitor external environmental conditions (DUB-A-UC1), Monitor internal environmental conditions (DUB-A-UC2), Manage and monitor HVAC performance (DUB-A-UC3). Observe waste management performance (DUB-A-UC4).

B. EV Grid Ecosystem: Creates a virtual representation of the physical grid assets and their interactions with electric vehicles (EVs). Through real-time monitoring, simulation, optimization, and prediction of grid performance, this digital twin aims to enhance the reliability and resilience of the energy grid. The DT supports environmental objectives, enabling reductions in carbon emissions via smarter design and operational practices. By analysing energy flows between EVs and charging infrastructure, the system helps optimize charging processes for greater efficiency in terms of both time and energy use.

Use Cases: Manage and track car park usage (DUB-B-UC1), Monitor charging stations (DUB-B-UC2), Monitor energy flow to and from EVs (DUB-B-UC3).

C. Behaviour and Life-Work Quality: Focuses on improving the quality of life and work for office staff by monitoring various factors such as occupancy, elevator usage, incident reporting, food intake, and environmental enhancements like air purifiers and plants. By integrating these data

streams with insights from other systems, the DT provides a holistic view of the workplace environment. Organizations can use insights to identify patterns, optimize operations, and create supportive, fulfilling workspaces. This approach enhances employee well-being and supports a healthier, more productive work environment.

Use Cases: Analyse and optimize canteen food usage (DUB-C-UC1), Monitor occupancy levels (DUB-C-UC2), Manage incident reporting and tracking (DUB-C-UC3), Record elevator usage (DUB-C-UC4), Track environmental quality enhancements (DUB-C-UC5).

D. Energy Flow Monitoring: Optimises energy consumption and production using virtual representations of real-time energy dynamics. The system aims to decarbonize energy systems, enhance renewable energy usage, and improve the reliability and efficiency of energy operations. Energy flows are monitored at multiple levels, from production sites like photovoltaic (PV) systems to building-level energy bills. Smart devices, such as energy-monitoring televisions, contribute to the digital twin's capabilities by providing granular consumption data.

Use Cases: Monitor energy flow, costs, and storage (DUB-D-UC1), Track energy consumption by devices (DUB-D-UC2), Monitor energy exchanges between digital twins (DUB-D-UC3), Control systems remotely to avoid peak demand (DUB-D-UC4) .

3.1.4 Dublin LL Stakeholders

The current organizational structure of the Dublin Living Lab (LL1), focusing on key actors and their primary responsibilities is given in Table 3:

Primary Stakeholders and Roles		
Organization	Category	Primary Responsibilities
Dún Laoghaire-Rathdown County Council (DLR COCO)	Living Lab Main Stakeholder	- Living Lab implementation leadership and coordination
		- Estate facilities management and EV fleet
		- Internal energy management and oversight
		- Executive management through Chief Executive and Directors of Service
University College Dublin (UCD)	Academic Partner	- Academic expertise provision
		- Research activities and workshops
		- Social and technological KPI evaluation
		- Project implementation support
		- Building-Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV) implementation

Fraunhofer Institute (FRHF)	Technology Provider	- Technical specifications development - Technology integration support
BEEPLANET (BEE)	Technology Provider	- Battery bank systems provision - Installation and implementation of energy storage solutions including container
CIDAUT	Technology Provider	- EV charging infrastructure development - Microgrid connectivity implementation - Insulation solutions provision
BOVLABS (BOV)	Technology Provider	- Energy trading platform development and implementation
SOPREMA (SOP)	Technology Provider	- Insulation materials and solutions supply
Supporting Stakeholders		
Organization	Category	Role
Dublin Metropolitan Climate Action Regional Office (CARO)	Governance Body	Regional climate initiatives coordination and strategy development
Codema (Dublin's Energy Agency)	Advisory	Energy efficiency expertise and sustainability guidance
Smart Dublin	Support and Advisory	Smart city initiatives
End Users and Beneficiaries		
Stakeholder Group	Description	Interaction Type
Council Staff	Direct users of council buildings	Primary facility users
Library Members	Users of council services	Service beneficiaries
Social Housing Tenants	Residents of council properties	Direct beneficiaries
General Public	Community members	Indirect beneficiaries

Table 3: Dublin Stakeholders

3.2.1 Madrid LL Technologies Deployment

The Madrid Living Lab (LL2) integrates a large portfolio of sustainable technologies and practices within urban development. Located in the Madrid Nuevo Norte district, LL2 prioritizes innovative solutions such as low-carbon concrete and asphalt, reclaimed insulation materials, and a geothermal district heating and cooling (DHC) network. These efforts align with PROBONO's goals of fostering energy efficiency, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and advancing circular economy principles. The Living Lab integrates advanced Digital Twin (DT) technologies for real-time monitoring and predictive analytics, enabling efficient management of demolition, construction, and operational phases. Key initiatives include materials workflow tracking, environmental impact assessments, and user engagement to promote energy-conscious behaviours. The incorporation of community-driven social innovations ensures that the project reflects local needs while advancing sustainability. Figure 25 is the Madrid LL Gantt chart of the innovations, while their matching descriptions are presented in the following.

3.2.1.1 M1-Low Carbon concrete

The low carbon concrete technology installation at the Madrid Living Lab (LL) focuses on reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions associated with concrete use in the District Heating and Cooling (DHC) system, particularly within the geothermal module. This initiative, developed by ACCIONA I+D and CELSA as

Figure 26: Low Carbon Concrete

part of Task 3.4 (Building Materials/Upcycling), addresses the fact that concrete alone contributes to over 30% of the GHG emissions initially calculated for the DHC system. To minimize environmental impact, the initiative targets a 20% reduction in CO₂ equivalent emissions by using low carbon concrete mixes across several structural components, including: (a) Reinforced concrete beams, (b) Solid reinforced concrete slabs, (c) Reinforced concrete foundation slabs, (d) Reinforced concrete walls, and (e) Reinforced concrete in retaining walls.

The sustainability strategy incorporates a circular economy approach by using non-primary materials such as recycled and artificial aggregates. Recycled aggregates will be sourced from concrete waste, while artificial aggregates will consist of black slags from steel production. Additionally, the concrete mixtures will replace Ordinary Portland Cement (CEM I/OPC) with low carbon alternatives, including supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs), further reducing the embodied carbon.

The technical and environmental performance of the low carbon concrete will be thoroughly assessed to ensure durability and adherence to Spanish regulatory standards, including:

- Spanish Structural Code (RD 470/2021)
- UNE-EN 12620:2002+A1:2008 (Aggregates for Concrete)

Comprehensive material testing will confirm that secondary materials meet performance criteria and that the structural integrity of the construction elements is maintained.

Risks: (a) Ensuring the quality and performance of low carbon concrete mixes, particularly for structural components like beams, slabs, and walls; (b) Compliance with Spanish regulatory standards (RD 470/2021 and UNE-EN 12620:2002+A1:2008); (c) Supply chain risks related to recycled and artificial aggregates, such as availability of black slags and variability in recycled concrete waste quality; (d) Durability concerns, including shrinkage, water absorption, and long-term performance in high-stress applications; (e) Coordination challenges during implementation in the geothermal module of the District Heating and Cooling (DHC) network.

3.2.1.2 M2 - Low Carbon Asphalt

The low carbon asphalt technology at the Madrid Living Lab focuses on reducing the environmental impact of road paving during the installation of the District Heating and Cooling (DHC) infrastructure. This sustainable construction approach is being developed by PROBONO partners ACCIONA I+D and CELSA, emphasizing a circular economy model that minimizes raw material use, lowers carbon emissions, and promotes resource efficiency through recycling and material reuse.

The asphalt technology will be applied as part of the road repositioning process following the installation of DHC pipes, with low carbon asphalt mixtures applied across multiple structural layers, including the surface, binder, and base. To achieve a minimum 20% reduction in CO₂ emissions while maintaining long-term road durability, the asphalt mixtures will incorporate medium to high rates of reclaimed asphalt (RA) sourced from old pavements, as well as recycled concrete aggregates. Recycled aggregates from concrete waste will also be used as secondary

materials to replace natural graded aggregates in the subbase. Additionally, black slags from steel production will partially replace natural aggregates, and supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs), such as fly ash and steel production slags, will be used as alternatives to Ordinary Portland Cement (CEM I/OPC).

This integrated approach improves both sustainability and cost-efficiency by reducing the carbon footprint of pavement construction while addressing the environmental impact and costs associated with waste generation and disposal. By facilitating the reuse of construction materials, ACCIONA I+D and CELSA aim to make asphalt recycling technologies more commercially viable and effective for widespread adoption.

To ensure both technical performance and environmental impact reduction, the low carbon asphalt materials will undergo rigorous testing for compliance with Spanish regulatory standards, including:

- Spanish Specifications for Road and Bridge Construction (PG-3 and PG-4)
- UNE-EN 13043:2003 (Aggregates for Bituminous Mixtures)

The testing process will verify that the inclusion of secondary materials, including reclaimed asphalt and recycled concrete aggregates, does not compromise the final properties of the asphalt while meeting national safety, durability, and performance requirements.

Low Carbon concrete and reclaimed asphalt will be implemented in the construction of the geothermal module of the DHC. DHC construction will take place by 2026.

Risks: (a) Variability in the quality of reclaimed asphalt (RA) and recycled concrete aggregates used in road paving; (b) Integration of black slags and supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) while maintaining road performance and durability; (c) Compliance with Spanish Specifications for Road and Bridge Construction (PG-3, PG-4) and UNE-EN 13043:2003; (d) Logistics and cost management in sourcing and transporting recycled materials; (e) Long-term monitoring to ensure that the asphalt retains its structural and environmental performance under high traffic loads.

3.2.1.3 M3 – Reclaimed Insulation

The "Reclaimed Insulation" initiative in the Madrid Living Lab focuses on developing sustainable construction materials for the work shed during the construction phase. CIDAUT is developing advanced insulation solutions using foam and composite systems that incorporate plastic waste with limited recyclability. By integrating secondary raw materials into the production process,

this approach significantly reduces CO₂ emissions while addressing sustainability challenges such as waste management, biodiversity loss, and climate change. A core component of the reclaimed insulation project is enhancing energy efficiency through improved thermal insulation. The advanced materials used not only reduce the carbon footprint of the construction process but also contribute to long-term energy savings by improving the thermal performance of temporary and permanent structures.

The reclaimed insulation strategy aligns with circular economy principles by reducing the need for virgin resources and emphasizing the reuse of waste materials. This approach directly supports PROBONO's objective of minimizing environmental impact across the construction sector.

In line with its commitment to sustainability, CIDAUT has developed a CO₂ emission calculator designed to estimate the environmental impact associated with fuel consumption in construction machinery. The tool considers both direct emissions (Tank-to-Wheel) and indirect emissions (Well-to-Tank) from fuel production, transport, and distribution. Additionally, it factors in the ownership and operational costs for vehicles with different propulsion systems, helping users make informed decisions from both economic and environmental perspectives.

Reclaimed insulation during construction phase. According to the Madrid LL timeline, DHC construction will take place by 2026, so these innovations will be implemented by 2026 as part of the work site.

Risks: (a) Availability of secondary raw materials, such as plastic waste with low recyclability; (b) Regulatory compliance for the use of advanced foam and composite insulation systems; (c) Integration of the reclaimed insulation within temporary and permanent structures during construction.

3.2.1.4 M4 – Electric Vehicles

The electric vehicles activity in the Madrid Living Lab, led by CIDAUT, focuses on developing a comprehensive electric vehicle (EV) charging infrastructure aimed at reducing carbon emissions and enhancing energy efficiency within the district. The technology installation includes the implementation of bidirectional charging technology (Vehicle-to-Grid or V2G), enabling EVs to both charge and return electricity to the grid during peak demand periods, and the integration of second-life batteries as energy storage solutions to complement the grid's energy balance and improve resource efficiency. A dynamic energy management system will be optimising energy flow, balancing supply from renewable sources with stored energy. To support this

infrastructure, consultancy services are required for the design and installation of a network that accommodates both standard and bidirectional chargers while meeting safety and performance standards. Safety evaluations will cover chargers, battery packs, and operational environments, ensuring full compliance with Spanish electrical infrastructure regulations. Scalability considerations will be addressed, allowing the charging network to expand alongside the growth of the EV fleet. The initiative also emphasizes circular economy principles by extending the lifecycle of battery components while promoting cleaner transport options and grid flexibility, contributing directly to PROBONO's sustainability goals.

Risks: (a) Ensuring compatibility of chargers with diverse EV models and second-life batteries; (b) Long-term maintenance and scalability of the EV charging infrastructure; (c) Safety and compliance with Spanish electrical infrastructure standards; (d) Potential delays in deploying second-life batteries for grid energy management.

3.2.1.5 M5 – 2nd Life Batteries

The initiative aligns with the broader goals of the Madrid Living Lab by supporting circular economy principles through the reuse of existing battery components, reducing the demand for new raw materials while providing a sustainable solution for temporary energy storage. It is led by BEE under Task 4.5 GBN Energy Storage, aims to enhance energy management and reduce carbon emissions by

Figure 27: Second Life Batteries

repurposing used electric vehicle (EV) lithium-ion batteries for stationary energy storage applications (Figure 27). Initially, these batteries were intended for integration within the geothermal module of the District Heating and Cooling (DHC) network. However, due to safety concerns raised by the DHC network designer (IDOM), they will now be deployed at the construction site to provide temporary energy storage during construction phases. The second-life batteries will be installed in a containerized format to ensure safe operation and compliance with site conditions, which introduces additional costs not originally accounted for. The batteries will support electricity management during the construction phase, providing backup power and peak shaving capabilities, contributing to a reduction in carbon emissions and operational costs. To ensure safe and effective implementation, several requirements have been outlined. The batteries will need to be transported with a truck capable of handling loads over 3,500 kg and

placed using a pallet truck or crane for positioning. The storage area must meet safety standards, including proper ventilation, temperature control (10-30°C), and fire detection systems. Electrical and communication connections must be ensured, with the inverter located no more than 5 meters from the battery system and proper internet connectivity for remote monitoring. Second life batteries will be implemented during the construction phase of the DHC to storage energy generated by PV panels.

Risks: (a) Transport and installation challenges, including compliance with safety standards for heavy and temperature-sensitive equipment; (b) Managing additional costs for containerized storage and installation; (c) Safety risks related to aging battery components and fire detection systems; (d) Limited operational life and performance of second-life batteries during temporary energy storage; (e) Ensuring proper communication and monitoring connections for battery management systems and with the Digital Twin.

3.2.1.6 M6 – Model Material Movements

The model for optimizing material movements during the construction phase at the Madrid Living Lab, developed by VLTN as part of Task 3.3, aims to assess the impact of material logistics on emissions, costs, and project timelines. This model will be implemented between 2025 and 2026 and is designed to support decision-making regarding construction logistics, with a focus on reducing carbon emissions and improving operational efficiency. A complementary tool developed under Task 3.3 by VLTN focuses on optimizing the demolition of existing structures and maximizing the reuse of materials. This approach aligns with circular economy principles by identifying materials suitable for reuse and minimizing waste generation during the deconstruction phase.

Both models emphasize sustainability by targeting the reduction of embodied carbon in construction processes while ensuring cost efficiency and adherence to project timelines. Their implementation is part of a broader strategy to incorporate innovative technologies that support the Madrid Living Lab's low-carbon construction goals.

Risks: (a) Accuracy of emissions and cost assessments during material logistics optimization; (b) Effective integration of models with existing construction workflows; (c) Timely training and adoption by stakeholders to use the optimization tools; (d) Validation and real-world applicability of the logistics model to meet construction timelines and sustainability goals.

3.2.1.7 M7 – Model demolition existing building

The demolition model for existing buildings in the Madrid Living Lab, developed by VLTN under Task 3.3, is designed to assess material reuse potential while minimizing waste generation and carbon emissions during the deconstruction phase. It prioritizes the optimization of material logistics by ensuring that reusable materials are effectively identified, catalogued, and integrated into future construction projects, contributing to a circular economy approach. At the core of the model is a Geographical Information System (GIS) database that catalogues materials from buildings and infrastructure scheduled for demolition. This database provides detailed information on material types, quantities, and their potential for recycling or reuse. By emphasizing the recovery of secondary raw materials from construction and demolition waste (C&DW), the model helps reduce the demand for raw material extraction while simultaneously lowering both carbon emissions and project costs. The model also incorporates dynamic visualization capabilities, allowing users to map planned demolition activities and overlay multiple data layers, such as weather patterns, climate conditions, and site-specific metadata like demolition timelines and building characteristics. These features enable a comprehensive assessment of potential environmental impacts. A key innovation within the model is its integration with a Digital Twin (DT) developed by the University of Santiago de Compostela (USC). The DT simulates pollutant emissions and dust and contaminants dispersion during demolition activities, using real-time data from low-cost environmental sensors and climate models to predict emission points. For simulation configuration, approved users can specify input parameters such as date and time of the demolition, location, surface area, and building height, type and quantity of particles released into the atmosphere. These inputs form the basis for contamination dispersion modelling. Real-time meteorological data is used to simulate contaminant dispersion and once the demolition plan and meteorological data are specified, the DT server runs the simulations of contaminant dispersion. The simulation process takes 15 minutes to 1 hour, depending on the complexity of the plan and the meteorological conditions. The results are made available via THREDDS and ERDDAP services for easy access and integration. This data-driven approach allows for proactive mitigation strategies, such as adjusting demolition schedules based on weather patterns and population density, to minimize public health risks and environmental harm. Implementation of the model, scheduled for 2025 to 2026, will focus on improving operational efficiency, reducing embodied carbon, and supporting sustainable material management practices, aligning closely with the Madrid Living Lab's broader sustainability objectives.

Risks: (a) Ensuring accurate identification and cataloguing of reusable materials via GIS databases; (b) Integration of demolition activities with material reuse plans to minimize waste; (c) Regulatory compliance for demolition and recycling processes; (d) Mitigating environmental and public health risks through real-time pollutant dispersion modelling using Digital Twin (DT) simulations; (e) Coordination of demolition schedules with weather and population density data to reduce adverse impacts.

3.2.1.8 M8 – DT DHC Network

Figure 28: DHC Network

The Digital Twin (DT) for the optimization of the District Heating and Cooling (DHC) network operations (Figure 28). This DHC will cover the thermal demand of 2 buildings (30.000 m² buildability). The Digital Twin contributes to operational efficiency by supporting the dynamic optimization of the geothermal DHC network. It enables better energy management by monitoring heat and cold distribution, flow rates, and temperature differentials across the system. This allows for proactive adjustments to maintain optimal energy performance while minimizing emissions. CARTIF is responsible for developing the Digital Twin for the operational part of the Geothermal network in the Madrid Living Lab (LL). The process begins with analysing the technical project of the geothermal network and the building design, followed by modelling the thermal demand in TRNSYS. The geothermal network will then be modelled in TRNSYS, and preliminary simulations of its operation will be conducted to analyse expected performance. Technical KPIs are defined along with monitoring plans for data collection. Monitoring systems will be deployed, installed, and commissioned based on these plans. Once the geothermal network is operational, data are collected and stored on the WP5 data platform. This data is used to calibrate the simulation model. The calibrated model predicts real system behaviour,

identifies any malfunctions or deviations, and provides recommendations to the operator through a decision support system based on the defined KPIs.

Risks: (a) Ensuring the DT's operational readiness for supporting geothermal DHC energy management; **b) Data Accuracy Risk:** Inaccurate data could lead to incorrect calibration of the simulation model, affecting predictions and decisions. c) **Integration Risk:** Challenges in integrating monitoring systems with existing infrastructure may cause delays or technical issues, impacting data collection and system performance.

3.2.1.9 M9 – DT reduce environmental impact

The Digital Twin (DT) is specifically designed to reduce environmental impacts during construction. Developed under Work Package 5 (WP5) and led by the University of Santiago de Compostela (USC), the DT provides real-time monitoring and predictive analytics to support low-carbon construction management. The DT aligns with the Madrid Living Lab's sustainability objectives by reducing greenhouse gas emissions, enhancing resource efficiency, and supporting data-driven decision-making throughout both the construction and operational phases.

The DT integrates data from various sources, including low-cost environmental sensors, climate models, and the Madrid City Council's air quality monitoring stations. It is capable of simulating pollutant emissions and dust generation during construction activities, which allows the project team to implement mitigation strategies and reduce the environmental impact on surrounding areas.

Risks: (a) Sensor connectivity and reliability for tracking emissions and environmental impacts during construction; (b) Data governance, privacy, and integration challenges with real-time monitoring systems; (d) Potential misalignment between simulation predictions and real-world environmental conditions.

3.2.1.10 M10 – DT heat island effect model

The Heat Island Effect Digital Twin (DT) model in the Madrid Living Lab, being developed by the University of Santiago de Compostela (USC), aims to assess and mitigate urban heat island effects during the construction and operational phases. Supports sustainability by reducing localized heat stress, improving urban comfort, and supporting data-driven planning for energy efficiency and environmental health across the district.

The model utilizes satellite temperature data with a 1 km resolution, further enhanced using machine learning and satellite imaging to improve accuracy to 10-15 square meters. By

integrating data from the urbanization project, the model provides real-time analysis of heat retention and distribution patterns within the living lab area. This allows for proactive mitigation strategies during the design phase to minimize heat accumulation, such as increased use of reflective materials, vegetation, and improved ventilation strategies.

Risks: (a) Data accuracy and resolution in the modelling of heat retention and distribution; (b) Integration of urbanization project data with real-time satellite imaging and climate data; (c) Ensuring stakeholder adoption of heat island mitigation strategies; (d) Maintenance of sensors and analytical tools for monitoring.

3.2.1.11 M11 – Geothermal Heat Pump

The geothermal heat pump system at the Madrid Living Lab is a key component of the District Heating and Cooling (DHC) network, designed to maximize energy efficiency and reduce carbon emissions using low-enthalpy geothermal energy. The system includes five water-to-

Figure 29: Temperature control of the geothermal pumps

water heat pumps, each with a thermal capacity of 85 kW, arranged in parallel (one as backup) with variable speed compressors for optimized energy management (see Figure 29). These pumps are responsible for generating both hot water (50°C supply, 40°C return) and cold water (5°C supply, 15°C return) for the district network.

A critical feature of the geothermal heat pump system is its integration with the geothermal borehole field, where excess heat can be dissipated during high cooling demand, and heat can be captured when heating demand is higher than cooling needs. The geothermal module includes two plate heat exchangers to manage heat transfer between the heat pumps and the borehole field, ensuring balanced energy exchange and efficient system performance.

The control system manages the number of operating heat pumps to maintain desired temperature set points while regulating the speed of both geothermal hydraulic pumps and distribution pumps for optimal energy delivery to connected buildings. The entire setup is configured to handle fluctuating thermal demands while minimizing energy losses.

The geothermal module itself is a buried technical space of approximately 60 m², designed to blend seamlessly with the landscape. It includes dedicated rooms for mechanical equipment, electrical distribution, and telecommunications, ensuring all system components are safely housed and operationally efficient. This system is a core innovation in the Madrid Living Lab's effort to achieve a zero-carbon district by integrating renewable energy sources with state-of-the-art energy management technologies. Geothermal Heat pumps will be implemented in the construction of the geothermal module of the DHC. Information of the geothermal heat pumps is available from the technology provider.

Risks: (a) Ensuring seamless integration of heat pumps with geothermal borehole systems and plate heat exchangers; (b) Maintaining optimal system performance during fluctuating heating and cooling demands; (c) Regulatory and safety compliance for renewable energy systems.

3.2.1.12 M12 – Geothermal DHC Network

The geothermal District Heating and Cooling (DHC) network at the Madrid Living Lab is designed to deliver renewable thermal energy using low-enthalpy geothermal sources, contributing to the realization of a zero-carbon energy system. The design and construction of the network are managed by two key PROBONO partners: IDOM, responsible for the design, and Acciona Construction, leading the construction efforts. The design prioritizes resource efficiency and sustainability, emphasizing the reuse of existing materials from deconstructed buildings and infrastructure. A material classification tool, developed for Madrid Nuevo Norte (MNN), will guide the deconstruction process by identifying materials suitable for reuse, treatment, and recycling. The innovation aligns with the highest sustainability standards, incorporating Level(s) and DGNB certification frameworks for resource optimization and life cycle performance benchmarking. Additionally, Madrid Nuevo Norte is already registered to pursue LEED Cities and Communities and BREEAM ES certifications, with the goal of achieving the highest qualification ratings in both systems.

The DHC network integrates a geothermal module, a distribution network, and building connections to ensure optimal energy efficiency and minimal carbon emissions. Within the geothermal module, five ECOF water-to-water heat pumps will be installed, each with a thermal capacity of 85 kW, operating in parallel with one unit as a backup. These heat pumps utilize the thermal energy stored in the ground to provide heating, domestic hot water (DHW), and cooling. Their internal refrigeration circuit connects to a closed-loop vertical borehole system that serves as both a heat source and heat dissipation medium, ensuring efficient thermal management

throughout the network. The distribution network consists of a four-pipe system designed for simultaneous heating and cooling supply. Additionally, a two-pipe borehole circuit facilitates efficient energy exchange between the geothermal wells and the heat pumps. Boreholes are grouped into clusters of five, each equipped with energy control valves for precise monitoring of water flow, heat transfer efficiency, and temperature regulation. The DHC network also incorporates a Renewable Energy Community (REC) governance model, supporting local energy management, cost efficiency, and collaborative resource use. This comprehensive design not only reduces reliance on fossil fuels but also prioritizes operational energy efficiency, aligning with sustainable, low-carbon urban development. The detailed design of the DHC was submitted in 2023. Some adaptations were done during 2024. According to the Madrid LL timeline, construction will start by 2026, so the assessment of the LCC will be done with the project costs currently available, to be implemented and completed.

Risks: (a) Ensuring successful reuse of deconstructed building materials guided by material classification tools; (b) Compliance with sustainability certification frameworks such as LEED; (c) Coordination between design and construction teams for smooth project execution; (e) Monitoring energy performance and cost efficiency during operation.

3.2.1.13 M13 – Social Innovations

The social innovations implemented at the Madrid Living Lab aim to foster community engagement, sustainability awareness, and inclusive participation in the transition towards a Green Building Neighbourhood (GBN). These initiatives are structured around participatory approaches such as the Geodesign workshop and citizen surveys, both of which involve direct collaboration with local communities, NGOs, and public authorities to co-design solutions and ensure local needs are reflected in the planning and decision-making processes.

The Geodesign workshop engages residents and stakeholders from the Madrid Nuevo Norte (MNN) area to collaboratively define requirements for the design of buildings and surrounding spaces. This process emphasizes shared decision-making and promotes the adoption of green infrastructure, renewable energy systems, and sustainable mobility options. Outcomes from the workshop directly inform the procurement processes and design requirements for the Living Lab. A citizen survey was also conducted to capture public opinions on key sustainability aspects, including green infrastructure, energy generation, and community management models. The feedback gathered supports communication strategies and behavioural change interventions aimed at fostering long-term engagement with sustainability goals.

Risks: (a) Engaging diverse community stakeholders in participatory workshops and surveys; (b) Managing resistance to behavioural changes required for adopting sustainable practices; (c) Ensuring inclusivity and representativeness in co-design processes; (d) Aligning citizen feedback with procurement and design strategies for maximum sustainability impact.

3.2.2 Madrid LL Change Management

The Madrid Living Lab has identified some necessary modifications to its implementation plan, focusing on adapting the timeline and budget allocations while maintaining its sustainability goals.

The full implementation of the District Heating and Cooling (DHC) network remains a priority, with construction scheduled to begin in early 2025 and completion aligned with the timeline of PROBONO. However, due to external dependencies related to the completion of commercial and residential buildings, thermo-activation and renewable energy installations within the DHC network cannot be executed during PROBONO's timeframe.

Madrid has committed to completing these aspects outside the project timeline using alternative funding sources.

The evaluation of the geothermal plant outputs will be ensured through enhanced simulation and design activities within the Digital Twin model, providing reliable predictions and assessments in advance of actual construction. Load performance testing will be conducted on-site, without building connections, to validate the geothermal system's outputs and align with project KPIs. CARTIF will lead the development of the Digital Twin for the operational part of the geothermal network system, including the smart management platform, to support accurate evaluation and monitoring.

A model to optimize material logistics during the construction phase is being developed by VLTN, with specific use cases to assess impacts on emissions, costs, and timelines.

BEE energy storage technology will be implemented with modifications to suit urban development requirements, including the installation of an outdoor energy storage system container.

Resources originally allocated for building thermo-activation have been redistributed to support the above changes and other Living Lab initiatives.

3.2.1 Madrid LL methodology-based mapping

3.2.1.0 Innovations Mapping and KPIs

The ArchiMate schematic of ArchiMate design (Figure 30) shows an overall view of the innovations, the related locations of their testing and the main facilitators of those innovations, as described in section 3.2.1.

Figure 30: Madrid Innovations development

Each innovation installation and testing activity in the Living Lab (e.g. M1-Low Carbon Concrete) is linked with the main stakeholder (e.g. ACC), the location (e.g. LL2-Las Tablas Oeste), and the related asset which is the output of the work of an innovation related WP (e.g. 3f2. Materials applied to pavements). The diagram also provides information about the related PROBONO Milestone where each innovation installation is expected to be completed.

Figure 31: Madrid LL KPIs

Behind all those artifacts which have been given semantic meaning according to ArchiMate methodology, there is a complete model, which connects the different semantic element levels of the methodology, i.e. Motivation, Strategy, Business, Application, Technology and Implementation and Migration layers).

Figure 31 shows the list of KPIs that LL Madrid will be monitoring, in collaboration with WP6 (see Deliverable D6.x, and specifically D6.4).

3.2.1.1 Madrid LL Use cases and Data

Figure 32: Madrid Use Cases

Figure 33: Madrid Use Cases Datasets

The Madrid Living Lab (LL2) use cases (Figure 32 shows the top level use cases diagram, and Figure 33 shows the datasets related to those use cases as identified in task T5.1), are centred around two key high-level areas, each addressing critical aspects in the context of the Living Lab.

Madrid Destruction – Construction

A. Material Workflow Tracking, demolition, treatment and reuse: Distrito Castellana Norte (DCN) has established an on-site treatment plant to process construction and demolition waste (C&DW) from the Madrid Living Lab and surrounding areas. This initiative builds on DCN's

existing GIS and BIM-based tools, which inventory buildings and infrastructures slated for demolition. These tools enable transparent tracking of material flows, ensuring that recycled materials are properly separated, classified, and reused by demolition companies for new constructions. The process aims to maximize on-site recycling, reduce reliance on new raw materials, and minimize associated costs such as transportation and taxes. By fostering circular material workflows, this system establishes a sustainable model for material reuse at the neighbourhood scale.

B. Environmental Impact Tracking related to materials upcycling: Track and monitor embodied emissions across the entire building life cycle, from demolition and construction to future deconstruction phases. Using a Digital Twin, DCN collects and registers materials data following cradle-to-grave principles, supporting data-driven decisions from design to deconstruction. Enhanced versions of DCN's existing tools connect C&DW data with BIM representations of new building components, enabling a full life-cycle view of material reuse. The system calculates avoided environmental impacts through upcycling, promoting resource-efficient designs that prioritize sustainability in new building components and infrastructure.

C. Secondary Raw Materials Utilization Database: Create a centralized materials data hub to optimize the reuse of resources recovered from demolition and deconstruction activities. The hub categorizes materials by their recyclability, quality, and potential applications, ensuring compliance with building standards. This database also supports ACCIONA's efforts to develop low-carbon concrete mixes for building structures and pavements, maximizing the use of on-site recycled materials. Leveraging Madrid Nuevo Norte's existing material classification tools, this system guides designers and contractors through deconstruction, treatment, and reuse processes, reducing embodied emissions across the neighbourhood.

D. Demolition Environmental Impact Monitoring: LiDAR mapping technology is used to assess air quality during deconstruction and demolition activities. By measuring particulate matter, contaminants, and their concentrations, the system analyses aerosol propagation in both vertical and horizontal dimensions. Combined with meteorological data, the insights guide decisions to minimize embodied emissions, such as avoiding demolition on windy days. The Universidad de Santiago de Compostela (USC) collects on-site LiDAR data, validating satellite air quality measurements and extending this monitoring to include the construction phase, ensuring environmental impacts are managed throughout the project lifecycle.

Madrid Geothermal Plant

A. Heating Requirements Forecasting: Predict room-level thermal requirements using AI, optimizing thermal comfort while reducing energy consumption and environmental impact. By analysing weather forecasts, user patterns, and building characteristics (captured in BIM LoD300), the system forecasts room temperatures 24 hours in advance. This functionality enables the district heating and cooling network (DHCN) to efficiently manage heating and cooling demands, adapting to user needs and minimizing resource use.

B. DHCN Smart Management: The Digital Twin replicates the DHCN to calculate key performance indicators (KPIs) and optimize network operations. The system supports operators by providing actionable insights in three ways: calculating essential KPIs, offering optimization guidelines, and assisting in decision-making for efficient DHCN management. By leveraging AI and other data inputs, the system ensures optimal performance without requiring direct physical interactions, enhancing operational reliability and energy efficiency.

C. User Profiling for DHCN Reporting: Empower users by providing tailored insights into the DHCN's energy and economic performance. The Digital Twin gathers operational data from the network and connected buildings, presenting it through dashboards customized for renewable energy communities, individual users, and the public. Data is anonymized to comply with GDPR, ensuring privacy. Features include visualizing KPIs, reporting historical and current data, and offering energy-saving recommendations. By increasing awareness and fostering user engagement, the system promotes informed decisions and sustainable behaviour.

3.2.3 Madrid LL Stakeholders

The current organizational structure of the Madrid Living Lab (LL2), focusing on key actors and their primary responsibilities is given in Table 4.

Primary Stakeholders and Roles		
Organization	Category	Primary Responsibilities
Crea Madrid Nuevo Norte (CMNN)	Living Lab Main Stakeholder	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Oversees integration of innovations into urbanization project - Leads governance for Compensation Board - Manages urbanization projects in Las Tablas Oeste
IDOM INGENIERIA	Technology Provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Designs geothermal District Heating and Cooling (DHC) network - Supports system integration
ACCIONA I+D (ACC)	Technology Provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develops low-carbon concrete and asphalt - Conducts life cycle analysis (LCA) for infrastructure - Oversees LL technologies, construction, and operation
BEEPLANET (BEE)	Technology Provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supplies and implements second-life batteries for energy storage
ECOFORST (ECOF)	Technology Provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supplies and implements heat pump technology for geothermal DHC network
CIDAUT	Technology Provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluates low-emission machinery for urbanization construction - Designs geothermal and bidirectional charging stations
CARTIF	Technology Provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develops digital twin to optimize geothermal network operations - Leads monitoring and evaluation
CELSA	Technology Provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provides reclaimed asphalt and recycled aggregates for road construction
VLTN	Technology Provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Designs and implements the models for material movement and building demolition
University of Santiago (USC)	Research Partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develops heat island effect model - Implements environmental tool incl. sensors - Develops Digital Twin for demolition and construction
ANERDGY (ANE)	Design Consultant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conducts building geometry studies for optimized energy performance
STAM	Technology Provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supports Digital Twin design related to Electric demand and generation
SOPREMA (SOP)	Technology Provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supplies materials for nature-based geothermal solutions (NBS) integration
Supporting Stakeholders		
Organization	Category	Role
Madrid City Council / Municipality of Madrid	Local Authority	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supports integration of innovations into public urbanization processes - Provides legal support

		- Facilitates replication of innovations
Community of Madrid	Governance Body	- Supports development of legal, financial, and technical frameworks for large-scale projects
Madrid Subterra	Advisory Body	- Provides expertise in underground infrastructures
Plataforma Española de Eficiencia Energética	Advisory Body	- Advises on energy efficiency policies
ADHAC	Advisory Body	- Offers input on district heating and cooling systems
Community Groups in Las Tablas	Community Stakeholders	- Provides feedback via workshops and surveys for community infrastructure management
End Users and Beneficiaries		
Stakeholder Group	Description	Interaction Type
Future Residents	Occupants of Madrid Nuevo Norte	Primary beneficiaries of zero-emission buildings and geothermal energy infrastructure
Local Businesses	Businesses in Madrid Nuevo Norte	Users of energy-efficient infrastructure and low-carbon urban designs
General Public	Madrid citizens	Indirect beneficiaries of environmental and urban sustainability improvements

Table 4: Madrid LL Stakeholders

3.3 LL3 Porto

Porto LL timeplan		2024												2025												2026												Start-End																									
Partner	Major LL activities	Q1			Q2			Q3			Q4			Q1			Q2			Q3			Q4																																								
		25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60																										
SOP / CAPW	P1-Cool Roof Test (Cool roof with Bifacial PV)																																																													25	60
	Design & Procurement																																																													25	25
	Construction																																																													26	29
	Commissioning																																																													30	30
	Permits																																																													43	45
	Operation																																																													31	57
BLABS / CAPW	P2-V2G (Vehicle to Grid)																																																													25	60
	Design & Procurement																																																													27	43
	Construction																																																													44	44
	Commissioning																																																													45	45
	Operation																																																													46	57
BLABS / CAPW	P3-S2V (Solar to Vehicle)																																																													25	60
	Design & Procurement																																																													25	30
	Construction																																																													30	30
	Commissioning																																																													31	31
	Operation																																																													32	57
CAPW / FHRF	P4-BIPV (Building Integrated Photovoltaic)																																																													25	60
	Design & Procurement																																																													30	37
	Construction																																																													37	39
	Commissioning																																																													39	40
	Permits																																																													43	45
	Operation																																																													40	57
CAPW	P5-REC (Collective Auto consumption)																																																													25	60
	Design & Procurement																																																													31	36
	Permits																																																													25	42
	Operation																																																													43	57
CAPW	P6-2nd life batteries - EMS																																																													25	60
	Design & Procurement																																																													25	32
	Commissioning																																																													36	38
	Operation																																																													38	57
SONAE	P7-SEVH (Smart EV Hub)																																																													25	60
	Design & Procurement																																																													25	25
	Construction																																																													33	36
	Commissioning																																																													37	37
	Operation																																																													38	57
SONAE	P8-PCMs (Phase Change Materials)																																																													25	60
	Design & Procurement																																																													25	30
	Construction																																																													33	36
	Commissioning																																																													37	37
	Operation																																																													38	57
eBOS	P9-Inform Users about Energy Use																																																													25	60
KNT/ CAPW	Design																																																													25	39
	Implementation - Configuration																																																													25	42
	Deployment																																																													43	45
	Testing and evaluation																																																													46	57
SONAE/ SIN	P10-Social Innovations																																																													25	60
	House of Birds operation																																																													25	60
	Vegetable Garden operation																																																													25	60
	Green Wall operation																																																													25	60
	Open Community Lab selection phase																																																													25	60
	Campus Workshop - implemented in 2023																																																													25	60
	CERNA																																																													25	60

Figure 34: Porto LL Gantt Chart, M25 -M60

3.3.1 Porto LLs Technologies Deployment

The Porto Living Lab (LL3) advances urban sustainability through the integration of innovative energy technologies and user-centred solutions. Located at Sonae Campus in Maia, LL3 showcases cutting-edge systems such as Cool Roofs with bifacial photovoltaic (PV), Solar-to-Vehicle (S2V) mobility technologies, Building-Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV), Phase Change Materials and Second-Life Battery systems. These technologies collectively aim to optimize energy efficiency, reduce environmental impact, and support the transition to a decentralized renewable energy network. LL3 Porto performs real-time monitoring, performance evaluation, and simulation of energy systems using the DT. Figure 34 shows the Porto LL Gantt Chart, while all matching Porto innovations are presented in the following.

3.3.1.1 P1 – Cool Roof Test (Cool roof with Bifacial PV)

The Cool Roof technology developed by SOPREMA, is a cutting-edge intervention aimed at enhancing energy efficiency and sustainability in urban areas. The Cool Roof with Bifacial PVs is a key step toward achieving energy-positive buildings, leveraging innovative design and technology to advance renewable energy use and urban sustainability. By integrating bifacial photovoltaic (PV) panels into a reflective cool roof design, this solution optimizes solar energy capture while minimizing heat

Figure 35: LL3 Cool Roof with BIPV

absorption, thereby reducing cooling loads and improving overall building performance. The Cool Roof not only supports renewable energy generation but also contributes to urban heat island mitigation, fostering more sustainable and comfortable environments. Figure 35 shows the result of the installation that took place in the first half of 2024.

Technical Features: The Cool Roof with bifacial PV combines advanced technologies for energy optimization (a) Bifacial Photovoltaics (PV), which are panels capable of capturing radiation on both sides, generating electricity from sunlight reflected off the roof surface, maximizing energy output compared to traditional PV system, (b) Reflective Coating, with highly reflective materials to reduce heat absorption, lowering indoor temperatures and decreasing the need for air conditioning, (c) Energy Management Integration, the generated solar energy is fed into an Energy Management System (EMS) to support building operations and, where applicable, export

surplus energy to the grid or other connected systems. Two sets of bi-facial solar panels consisting of 26 panels in total were installed on the roof of a smart street building. The layout for the installation of the panels on the roof was defined allowing to split the surface in two different areas, one with cool roof layer applied and the other without any coverage. The chosen layout consists of two rows of 13 panels each, representing a total installed capacity of 10 kWp and a 4x16 m² Cool Roof surface.

Key functionalities include (a) Dual-Surface Energy Generation for enhancing energy efficiency by utilizing both direct sunlight and reflected light, (b) Thermal Load Reduction, by reflecting solar radiation, to reduce thermal stress on the building, improving occupant comfort and reducing cooling energy demands, and (c) Resilience to Climate Conditions, to withstand varying weather conditions, ensuring durability and consistent performance.

Risks: (a) Reflectivity and Glare that may impact surrounding areas or pedestrians, however, for this particular installation, the risk to pedestrians has been eliminated due to the high roof height, (b) System Integration, to ensure the seamless integration of bifacial PVs with existing energy management systems and grid infrastructure, and (c) Operational Efficiency, related to suboptimal performance during prolonged overcast conditions or low reflectivity environments.

3.3.1.2 P2 – Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G)

The Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technology developed by BLABS is an innovative solution that bridges the gap between electric vehicles (EVs) and the energy grid, advancing sustainability and energy efficiency in urban mobility systems. V2G enables bidirectional energy flow, allowing EVs to function as mobile energy storage units. This technology not only supports grid stabilization by feeding surplus energy back into the grid but also optimizes

Figure 36: Sonae Campus Maia - Smart Street.

energy consumption patterns for building and district-level systems. V2G contributes to a decentralized energy network, leveraging EVs to achieve energy balance and cost efficiency. Figure 36 shows the initiative location.

Technical Features: The V2G system incorporates advanced features for seamless energy integration: (a) Bidirectional Charging Technology allows EVs to discharge energy back to the

grid during peak hours and recharge during off-peak times, ensuring optimal energy use and cost savings, (b) Energy Management Integration, integrated with the local SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition) to coordinate energy flow between EVs, buildings, and the grid, and (c) Smart Charging Infrastructure, employing predictive algorithms to balance energy loads dynamically, minimizing strain on the grid and ensuring efficient energy use.

The Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technology will be deployed with a smart charger capable of handling bidirectional energy flow. The charger will be installed at designated location within the smart street area. The deployment will allow communication with the local SCADA, optimizing energy redistribution to match dynamic demand profiles. A pilot installation of up to 20 kW capacity is planned, enabling comprehensive testing of V2G functionalities. The current plan is for one 11kW charger.

Key Functionalities: The solution reduces energy costs for building operators and EV owners by leveraging off-peak energy rates and generating revenue from surplus energy fed back to the grid. It features: (a) Decentralized Energy Storage, enables EVs to act as distributed energy storage units, improving grid flexibility and reliability, (b) Peak Load Management, balances energy supply and demand by storing energy during low demand and feeding it back during peak hours.

Risks: (a) Grid Compatibility, to ensure that V2G systems are compatible with existing grid infrastructure and regulatory frameworks, (b) Battery Degradation, to manage the EV battery life while maintaining efficiency, (c) System integration, to ensure seamless communication and integration between the EVs, chargers, and the EMS for real-time energy flow management, and (d) V2G Charger Availability, due to the lack of commercially available V2G chargers, which poses a challenge for implementation.

3.3.1.3 P3 – Solar-to-Vehicle (S2V)

The Solar-to-Vehicle technology is a transformative step toward sustainable urban mobility, enabling EVs to harness clean solar energy and reducing reliance on traditional grid electricity. This solution supports the transition to a renewable energy-powered transportation system while offering significant environmental and economic advantages. The Solar-to-Vehicle (S2V) technology developed by BLABS is an innovative solution that

Figure 37: SV Installation- Smart Street.

integrates solar energy into electric vehicle, enabling EVs to charge from solar power generated by photovoltaic (PV) systems, reducing dependency on grid electricity and promoting sustainable energy use. By utilizing locally produced solar energy, S2V enhances energy efficiency, reduces greenhouse gas emissions, and supports the transition toward a clean energy ecosystem. Figure 37 shows the EV charger installed.

Technical Features: The Solar-to-Vehicle (S2V) system incorporates advanced technologies to streamline solar energy integration: (a) Solar Charging, allowing EVs to charge from locally generated solar energy, bypassing the grid and minimizing transmission losses, (b) Energy Storage Integration, with the capability to store surplus solar energy in batteries for use during low solar generation periods, and (c) Smart Charging Algorithms, optimizing charging schedules based on solar energy availability and EV demand to maximize efficiency.

The Solar-to-Vehicle system consists in a solar-powered charging station connected to the local PV installations. An S2V charger of 22 kW is under tests using the production capacity reserved from other small pilots, totalling approximately 20 kWp, to power the vehicles. It is being implemented through the following models (a) 100% S2V: Charging is feasible during moments of local photovoltaic production to initiate the charging process, (b) S2V and grid energy: The operating mode is configured by the operator, combining green energy with grid energy. The S2V system will connect to the Metering Control Centre (MCC) for real-time monitoring and optimization.

Key Functionalities: The Solar-to-Vehicle solution provides significant environmental and operational benefits, including: (a) Renewable Energy Utilization, ensuring that EVs are primarily charged using clean solar energy, reducing carbon footprints, (b) Cost Savings, by lowering dependence on grid electricity and leveraging free solar energy, and (c) Grid Independence, enabling EV charging in remote locations or during grid outages through on-site solar and storage systems.

Risks: (a) Solar Variability, addressing the impact of inconsistent solar energy generation due to weather conditions or shading, (b) System Integration, ensuring seamless connectivity between PV systems, chargers, and the EMS for efficient energy management, and (c) Infrastructure Costs, managing the initial capital required for the installation of solar-powered charging stations.

3.3.1.4 P4 – Building-Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV)

The BIPV technology is a pivotal innovation in sustainable urban development, offering a harmonious blend of renewable energy production and architectural aesthetics. BIPV solutions integrate solar energy generation seamlessly into building structures, transforming façades, roofs, and other architectural elements into active energy producers. This technology supports the transition toward energy-efficient buildings, contributing to urban sustainability goals, enabling buildings to achieve nearly zero-energy or energy-positive performance.

Figure 38: Façade location for BIPV - Smart Street.

Technical Features: The BIPV system incorporates cutting-edge technologies for efficient energy production and integration: (a) Photovoltaic Modules, embedded directly into building components, including façades and roofs, allowing seamless integration with architectural design, (b) Customizable Design, offering flexibility in terms of size, shape, and color to match building aesthetics, and (c) Integration with local SCADA, enabling real-time monitoring and optimization of energy production and consumption.

In this initiative, the BIPV system will involve the installation of PV modules as part of building envelope in the selected building presented in Figure 38. A total capacity of approximately 15 kWp will be deployed, with PV modules strategically integrated into south-facing façades to maximize solar energy capture. The system will connect to the SCADA, ensuring optimal energy flow management between the building and the grid.

Key Functionalities: The BIPV technology offers several benefits: (a) Renewable Energy Generation, by utilizing building surfaces to generate clean electricity, reducing reliance on fossil fuels, (b) Aesthetic Integration, maintaining the architectural integrity of buildings while incorporating energy generation capabilities, and (c) Reduced Energy Costs, through on-site solar energy production, leading to significant savings on electricity bills.

Risks: (a) Structural Integration, ensuring the BIPV modules are compatible with the building design and construction standards, (b) Efficiency Loss, managing potential performance reductions due to shading or suboptimal installation angles, and (c) Maintenance and Durability,

addressing challenges related to maintaining and replacing BIPV modules integrated into building structures.

3.3.1.5 P5 – REC, Collective Auto Consumption

The Collective Auto Consumption (REC) initiative led by CAPW, is an innovative solution designed to enhance energy efficiency and promote the shared use of renewable energy in urban communities. REC facilitates the collective use of locally generated energy, enabling groups of buildings or users to share surplus electricity from photovoltaic systems. By

Figure 39: Delimited area for the REC members of SONAE campus

fostering decentralized energy consumption, this initiative reduces dependency on grid electricity, lowers energy costs, and supports the transition to sustainable energy systems. The REC initiative plays a critical role in advancing renewable energy adoption, contributing to urban energy resilience and sustainability. The location of the initiative is in the Sonae Campus and neighbourhood, local gym (Figure 39).

Technical Features: The REC management system incorporates advanced technologies and frameworks to streamline shared energy usage: (a) Peer-to-Peer Energy Sharing, enabling surplus energy generated by photovoltaics to be distributed among participating users within a defined geographical area, (b) MCC Integration, ensuring monitoring and optimization of energy distribution and consumption, and (c) Smart Metering and Data Analytics, providing detailed energy usage insights and enabling accurate billing for participants. In this initiative, permits and legal frameworks will be established to enable the collective use of energy within the designated pilot site. The community comprises three existing PV production units, with a combined power capacity of 5 MW. The REC management system allows the assessment of the energy savings within the community.

Key Functionalities: The REC initiative offers several transformative benefits: (a) Optimized Energy Utilization, enabling efficient use of locally generated renewable energy, reducing reliance on external grid power, (b) Cost Reduction, lowering electricity bills for participants by

sharing renewable energy resources, and (c) Community Energy Resilience, fostering energy independence and promoting collective energy security within urban communities.

Risks: (a) Regulatory Compliance, addressing legal and policy challenges related to collective energy consumption and sharing, and potential delay in the successful establishment of the community due to the long wait for permit approvals for community registrations (b) User Engagement, ensuring active participation and understanding of the system by all users, and (c) System Maintenance, managing the upkeep and reliability of shared energy infrastructure and smart metering systems.

3.3.1.6 P6 – Second Life Batteries

The Second Life Batteries is an innovative solution aimed at repurposing used electric vehicle (EV) batteries to create cost-effective, sustainable energy storage systems. By giving a second life to EV batteries, this initiative addresses the challenge of battery waste while providing an eco-friendly and efficient energy storage option for renewable energy systems. The Second Life Batteries contribute to enhancing energy efficiency, supporting grid stability, and promoting the circular economy in energy storage technology.

Technical Features: The Second Life Batteries system incorporates advanced technologies and processes to ensure optimal performance and integration: (a) Battery Repurposing Technology, where retired EV batteries are reconditioned and assembled into modular storage units, (b) Energy Storage Integration, enabling the batteries to store surplus energy from renewable sources such as photovoltaics (PVs), and (c) Energy Management System (EMS) Integration, for real-time monitoring and optimization of storage and discharge cycles.

Given the complexity inherent to the installation of battery units, which involves electrical infrastructure, climate-controlled areas, auxiliary equipment, etc., and considering the available budget, it was decided not to install a new set of batteries. Instead, the existing Second Life Batteries from BEE will be operated through the implementation of an Energy Management System (EMS) led by CAPW that optimizes their performance, increases self-consumption, and reduces energy consumption from the grid by prioritizing the storage of surplus energy produced by the installed PV system for use when needed.

The 2nd life batteries system has a capacity of 92 kWh and a 100 kW inverter. It is installed in the parking lot of Lote 4A, an office building within the SONAE Campus, which has its own PV production allowing for the testing of the previously described demonstration of self-consumption increase.

Key Functionalities: The Second Life Batteries initiative offers multiple benefits: (a) Circular Economy Contribution, by extending the lifecycle of EV batteries and reducing electronic waste and (b) Renewable Energy Optimization, enabling storage of surplus solar energy for use during peak demand or low solar generation periods.

Risks: (a) Battery Degradation, managing the variability in performance due to the age and prior usage of repurposed batteries, (b) System Integration, ensuring seamless operation with the EMS and other energy systems, and (c) Safety Concerns, addressing potential risks related to thermal management and electrical faults in second-life battery systems.

3.3.1.7 P7 – Smart EV Hub (SEVH)

The Smart EV Hub (SEVH) initiative, led by SON, is an advanced solution designed to integrate electric vehicles (EVs) seamlessly into the energy ecosystem. By combining smart charging infrastructure with advanced energy management, SEVH enables efficient EV charging while optimizing energy consumption. This initiative

Figure 40: Sonae Campus parking lot of logistics warehouse

supports the transition to sustainable urban mobility by optimizing energy usage, minimizing grid strain, and encouraging the adoption of EVs as a viable transportation alternative. Figure 40 shows the initiative location.

Technical Features: The Smart EV Hub system incorporates cutting-edge technology to enhance EV integration: (a) Smart Charging Stations, equipped with dynamic load management to distribute charging power efficiently across multiple vehicles, (b) Energy Management System (EMS) Integration, enabling real-time monitoring and optimization of charging processes to align with energy demand and supply.

A pilot Smart EV Hub will be deployed within the smart street building, featuring EV charging points with eight (8) type 2 chargers, supporting AC charging. The power of each charger is 11 kW being 88 kW the total power of the charging hub. The system will be equipped with intelligent software to manage charging schedules, prioritize renewable energy use, and balance

grid loads effectively. The pilot will also include infrastructure to facilitate V2G integration as part of future scalability.

Key Functionalities: The Smart EV Hub provides a range of benefits, including: (a) Optimized Charging Efficiency, ensuring equitable energy distribution among connected vehicles to reduce wait times and maximize charging capacity, (b) Renewable Energy Integration, leveraging solar or other green energy sources for EV charging, and (c) Peak Load Reduction, balancing energy supply and demand during peak periods to reduce grid stress.

Risks: (a) Grid Reliability, addressing potential challenges related to grid fluctuations caused by high EV charging demand, (b) User Adoption, ensuring user-friendly interfaces and reliable performance to encourage widespread EV adoption, and (c) Interoperability, managing seamless integration of diverse EV models and charging technologies within the Smart EV Hub.

3.3.1.8 P8 – Phase Change Materials (PCMs)

The Phase Change Materials (PCMs) initiative, led by SON, introduces an innovative approach to energy efficiency by leveraging materials with high thermal storage capacity to regulate building temperatures. PCMs store and release energy during phase transitions (e.g., from solid to liquid), reducing energy demands for heating and cooling systems. This initiative enhances energy performance and supports sustainable building practices by optimizing thermal energy management. The PCM technology will be implemented in a small-scale pilot, as proof of concept, in a supermarket store near the living lab.

The store has nearly 8,000 square meters and is also located in Maia, within a 4 km radius of the campus. Figure 41 shows the location of the initiative. This approach will allow to study the behaviour of the technology in a controlled environment and properly assess the impacts in energy savings. In parallel to having the measured impacts of the small pilot, a scale up to the logistics warehouse is also proposed. A comprehensive study will be conducted to determine the number and location of PCMs to install

Figure 41: MDL Maia Vivaci - Cold Chambers

in the building and the impact on the energy efficiency to calculate the energy benefits for the warehouse.

Technical Features: The PCM system incorporates: (a) High Thermal Storage Capacity, utilizing PCMs designed to store large amounts of thermal energy during phase changes, (b) Building Integration, embedding PCMs within construction elements such as walls, floors, or ceilings to optimize heat absorption and release, and (c) Energy Management System (EMS) Integration, enabling real-time monitoring and control of PCM performance.

Key Functionalities: The PCM offers multiple advantages: (a) Thermal Energy Optimization, reducing peaks in cooling demand by storing energy **and** releasing it when needed, (b) Reduced Energy Costs, decreasing the reliance on active heating and cooling systems, resulting in energy savings.

The pilot will be divided into two different stages: (a) Sizing and implementation in a small-scale environment, such as a supermarket. Thereby, it will be possible to better understand the behaviour of the PCM technology within the food retail environment and the corresponding flexibility following the restrictions of SON health and safe policies, and (b) Apply this know-how and simulate the impacts of the usage of PCMs in the food retail logistics warehouse while also studying and simulating energy management strategies for PCMs complemented with EVSEs and other systems (e.g., compressors, HVAC, etc.). Through the implementation of PCMs on the logistics warehouse the expected energy savings per year are 986.4 MWh/year.

Risks: (a) Material Performance, ensuring the durability and consistency of PCM behaviour over repeated phase transitions, (b) System Integration, managing the seamless incorporation of PCM panels into building designs and EMS, and (c) Cost-Effectiveness, balancing the initial investment in PCM materials with long-term energy savings and benefits.

3.3.1.9 P9 – Inform Users About Energy Use

The digital tool to Inform Users About Energy Use, (eBOS and KNT), aims to increase energy awareness and empower users to make informed decisions about their energy consumption. Leverages advanced monitoring and communication technologies to provide real-time insights into energy use patterns, enhance user engagement, and promote sustainable behaviours. By enabling users to visualize and understand their energy footprint, this initiative fosters a culture of energy efficiency and responsibility.

Features: The digital twin (DT) is used to promote behavioural change and to increase awareness for the community by providing the necessary information to make the best possible decisions

in terms of energy utilization. Examples include informing users about energy usage, providing recommendations about energy consumption, production on-site of renewable energy, and suggesting the best time to charge electric vehicles.

Risks: User Engagement, ensuring that the system is intuitive and accessible to encourage active participation and sustained use.

3.3.1.10 P10 – Social Innovations and Open Community Lab

The Social Innovations initiative (SON) focuses on fostering community engagement and promoting sustainability through innovative social and biodiversity projects. This initiative aims to create a positive impact on the well-being of individuals and communities while enhancing the environmental and architectural qualities of the Sonae Campus. By integrating educational

Figure 42: Sonae Campus Maia social innovations site.

and participatory elements, Social Innovations empower stakeholders to actively contribute to energy efficiency, biodiversity, and sustainable urban development. Figure 42 shows the innovations location.

Features: Social Innovations include diverse activities and infrastructures aimed at community involvement and environmental enhancement: (a) House of Birds, offering nesting areas to promote biodiversity and wildlife preservation, (b) Vegetable Garden, providing a space for team-building, learning, and community engagement, and (c) Green Wall, enhancing the aesthetic and environmental value of the campus by improving air quality and supporting urban greening, (d) Open Community Lab, a collaborative platform fostering innovation, learning, and community-driven sustainability projects, (e) Campus Workshop, with Interactive sessions designed to educate and engage stakeholders in energy efficiency and sustainable practices, (f) CERNA, an initiative to advance research and knowledge-sharing on sustainability and renewable energy within the campus, and (g) Newsletter, a communication channel to keep stakeholders informed about project progress, sustainability milestones, and upcoming events.

Risks: (a) Stakeholder Participation, ensuring active and consistent involvement from employees and local communities, (b) Maintenance and Longevity, addressing the long-term upkeep of biodiversity and social innovation projects, and (c) Scalability, evaluating the replicability of successful initiatives to other campuses or urban settings.

3.3.2 Porto LL Change Management

Initially, the mobility solutions were planned to be developed by an external technology provider under CAPW responsibility. However, BOV has now taken over this role, leveraging Project Management resources reallocated from the Madrid Living Lab to the Porto Living Lab. The inclusion of Solar-to-Vehicle (S2V) and Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technology from BOV will significantly enhance the energy profile and overall impact of the Porto Living Lab. This change requires no formal amendment, as it will be fully justified and technically detailed in the RP2 reporting period.

3.3.3 Porto LL methodology-based mapping

3.3.3.0 Innovations Mapping and KPIs

The ArchiMate schematic of ArchiMate design Figure 43 shows an overall view of the innovations, the related locations of their testing and the main facilitators of those innovations, as described in section 3.3.1.

Each innovation installation and testing activity in the Living Lab (e.g. P2-V2G) is linked with the main stakeholder (e.g. BLABS), the location (e.g. LL3-Sonae Campus Maia), and the related asset which is the output of the work of an innovation related WP (e.g. 4f1. V2G Mobility Charging Infrastructure with AI). The diagram also provides information about the related PROBONO Milestone where each innovation installation is expected to be completed.

Behind all those artifacts which have been given semantic meaning according to ArchiMate methodology, there is a complete model, which connects the different semantic element levels of the methodology, i.e. Motivation, Strategy, Business, Application, Technology and Implementation and Migration layers.

Figure 43: Porto Innovations Development

Figure 44 shows the list of KPIs that LL Porto will be monitoring, in collaboration with WP6 (see Deliverable D6.x, and specifically D6.4).

Figure 44: Porto LL KPIs

3.3.3.1 Porto LL Use cases and Data

Figure 45: Porto LL Datasets

Figure 46: Porto LL Use Cases

The Porto Living Lab (LL3) focuses on empowering users, monitoring innovative technologies, and optimizing energy systems within the Green Building Neighbourhood (GBN) framework. Leveraging a Digital Twin (DT), these efforts aim to foster energy efficiency, reduce environmental impact, and support sustainable urban development. The Living Lab use cases (Figure 46 shows the top level use cases diagram, and Figure 45 shows the datasets related to those use cases as identified in task T5.1), are centred around three key high-level areas, in the context of the Living Lab.

A. Influencing User Behaviour in Energy Consumption: The primary goal is to empower campus users with actionable information to make informed energy consumption decisions. By utilizing real-time inputs on energy production and consumption within the campus, a suite of tools will share critical data with users. This system encourages energy conservation and promotes consumption during community-beneficial times, helping to reduce peak loads.

The initiative emphasizes renewable energy production, reducing the carbon footprint, and aligning with Sonae Group's corporate sustainability targets. Users are also made aware of the company's environmental commitments, fostering a sense of involvement in collective sustainability actions.

Information dissemination occurs through user-friendly methods such as notifications on mobile apps, an internal website, or strategically placed campus monitors. This holistic approach integrates energy consumption and production data from various sources, centralizing it for user access.

Use Cases: (PTO-A-UC1) Inform users about their energy usage, providing transparency and insights, (PTO-A-UC2) Offer tailored recommendations to optimize energy consumption.

B. Monitoring the Innovations Tech-Hub: This high-level need centralizes the management and utilization of diverse technological innovations forming the tech-hub. These innovations include Solar-to-Vehicle (S2V) systems, Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technology, green hydrogen production, Building-Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV), second-life batteries, phase-change materials, and solar heating for industrial processes. A unified user interface aggregates data from these technologies, simplifying monitoring, performance evaluation, and fault detection. The tech-hub represents a microcosm of the future energy landscape, where diverse energy sources and consumers interact within a localized ecosystem.

Use Cases: (PTO-B-UC1) Monitor the tech-hub's performance and ensure smooth operation, (PTO-B-UC2) Detect performance issues and identify system failures to ensure reliability.

C. Simulating Energy System Modifications for Optimization: This high-level need enables stakeholders to simulate and assess potential modifications to the GBN energy system. Simulations include adding new devices (e.g., charging stations, HVAC systems), integrating new energy production units, updating existing tech-hub components (e.g., increasing battery capacity), and removing outdated devices. The simulation capabilities allow for testing the impact of these changes on energy consumption and performance, identifying inefficiencies, and optimizing energy use. Stakeholders can make informed decisions about future upgrades to physical twin components and zones, ensuring continuous improvement in energy performance.

Use Cases: (PTO-C-UC1) (a) Simulate system modifications, assess the impact of adding, removing, or updating energy devices, and (b) Identify optimization opportunities, highlight areas or components with high energy usage and recommend upgrades.

3.3.3.2 Porto LL Stakeholders

The current organizational structure of the Porto Living Lab (LL3), focusing on key actors and their primary responsibilities is given in Table 5.

Primary Stakeholders and Roles		
Organization	Category	Primary Responsibilities
SONAE Companies (SONAE)	Living Lab Main Stakeholder	- Hosts the Porto LL on the Sonae Campus
		- Provides resources for energy, biodiversity, and community initiatives
		- Creates a sustainable workplace environment
		- Supports better energy management
CAPWATT (CAPW)	Project Manager	- Manages energy-related pilots - Leads licensing, implementation, and monitoring of technologies
INESC TEC	Technology Provider	- Provides technical studies on Phase Change Materials (PCMs)
		- Oversees energy storage systems
		- Supports software development
SOPREMA (SOP)	Technology Provider	- Supplies and integrates cool roof technologies
		- Implements bi-facial PV solutions
BEEPLANET (BEE)	Technology Provider	- Supports integration of 2nd life batteries for energy storage
ELERGONE	Consulting	- Develops Smart EV Hub and software
		- Manages energy data and integration into control systems
University of Évora	Research Partner	- Conducts feasibility studies for Solar Heat for Industrial Processes (SHIP)
CHP Plant Experts	Internal Partner	- Provides specifications for hydrogen integration
		- Supports CHP plant enhancements
Technology Providers (various contractors)	External Partners	- Develop and supply solutions for Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G)
		- Implement Solar-to-Vehicle (S2V)
		- Design hydrogen systems
Supporting Stakeholders		
Organization	Category	Role
DGEG (Direção Geral de Energia e Geologia)	Regulatory Body	- Approves legal frameworks for Renewable Energy Communities and hydrogen production
Campus Architect	Internal Stakeholder	- Reviews and approves Building-Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV) installations
Maia City Council	Local Government	- Supports policy implementation
		- Facilitates green corridors and public parks
		- Engaged in testing and evaluating technologies

Universities, Research Institutions, and Startups	Community Stakeholders	- Participate in Social Innovation and Open Community Lab
Local Community	Community Stakeholders	- Engages in social innovation initiatives through Open Community Lab
End Users and Beneficiaries		
Stakeholder Group	Description	Interaction Type
Campus Employees	Workers on the Sonae Campus	- Primary users of sustainable technologies
		- Participants in biodiversity initiatives
		- Users of green and sustainable technologies
Campus Visitors	Guests to the Sonae Campus	Beneficiaries of improved spaces and renewable energy systems
Solidarity Associations	Community Beneficiaries	Recipients of produce from the campus vegetable garden

Table 5: Porto LL Stakeholders

3.4 LL4 Brussels

Brussels LL timeplan		2024												2025												2026												Start-End																									
Partner	Major LL activities	Q1			Q2			Q3			Q4			Q1			Q2			Q3			Q4			Start	End																																				
		25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48			49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60																								
SOP	B1-Cool Roof (Cool roof with Bifacial PV)																																																													25	60
	<i>Feasibility and Design</i>																																																														
	<i>Final Design and Plan</i>																																																														
	<i>Permits</i>																																																														
	<i>Contractor selector and Tendering</i>																																																														
	<i>Preparation and Construction</i>																																																														
	<i>Installation of PV panels</i>																																																														
	<i>Testing and Commissioning</i>																																																														
	<i>Monitoring and Maintenance</i>																																																														
FHRF	B2-PV Panels																																																													25	60
ACE	<i>Selection</i>																																																														
ACE	<i>Procurement and Installation</i>																																																														
	<i>Commissioning</i>																																																														
ACE	<i>Operation</i>																																																														
TPF	B3-Energy Monitoring System																																																													25	60
TPF	<i>Installation</i>																																																														
TPF	<i>Connection with Data Space</i>																																																														
TPF	<i>Operation</i>																																																														
Stam	<i>Analysis</i>																																																														
SIM	B4-Social Innovations (IEQ Study)																																																													25	60
TSERV	<i>Installation of IoT sensors</i>																																																														
SIM	<i>Baseline</i>																																																														
SIM	<i>Planning Interventions</i>																																																														
SIM	<i>Autumn Interventions</i>																																																														
SIM	<i>Analysis</i>																																																														
SIM	<i>Spring Interventions</i>																																																														
SIM	<i>Analysis</i>																																																														
SIM	<i>Validation evaluation publication</i>																																																														

Figure 47: Brussels LL Gantt Chart, M25 - M60

3.4.1 Brussels LL Technologies Deployment

The Brussels Living Lab (LL4) showcases sustainable urban building transformation. Located at the ACE School in Auderghem, LL4 focuses on integrating technologies such as Cool Roof systems with bifacial photovoltaic panels, advanced energy monitoring systems, and social innovations to enhance building performance and foster community engagement. Through the deployment of green building technologies and data-driven solutions, LL4 Brussels addresses challenges related to energy efficiency, indoor environmental quality, and urban biodiversity. Leveraging Digital Twin (DT) technology, the Living Lab facilitates real-time energy management and optimization while enabling informed decision-making for stakeholders. Figure 47 shows the Brussels LL Gantt Chart, for all innovations deployed in the Living Lab and listed in the following.

3.4.1.0 B1 – Cool Roof (Cool roof with Bifacial PV)

The Cool Roof Brussels LL initiative, led by SOPREMA, represents an innovative approach to optimizing energy efficiency and environmental sustainability in urban buildings. The technology integrates a green roof design with bifacial photovoltaic (PV) panels to achieve multiple objectives, including renewable energy generation, improved thermal comfort, and reduced carbon emissions. This solution addresses the challenges of outdated roofing systems by introducing advanced insulation and waterproofing technologies, while supporting rainwater retention and biodiversity. Figure 48 shows the initiative location, in ACE building.

Figure 48: ACE Building

Technical Features: The Cool Roof combines advanced design features: (a) Green Roof System: Incorporating high-evapotranspiration capabilities to enhance biodiversity and reduce urban heat islands. (b) Bifacial PV Panels: Utilizing both direct and reflected sunlight for increased solar energy generation, optimizing energy output for building operations. (c) Enhanced Insulation: Upgrading the existing roof insulation layer from 60 mm to 160 mm to meet current construction standards, ensuring better thermal performance and energy efficiency.

The implementation includes removing the gravel ballast and outdated insulation layers, followed by installing a new waterproofing system and the green roof solution. The 400 m² roof area will be divided into zones to accommodate PV panels and green coverage while ensuring access to technical installations for maintenance. The green roof layer will reduce rainwater runoff, protect the waterproof membrane from UV radiation, and improve acoustic insulation for classrooms located below.

Key Functionalities: The Cool Roof initiative provides several benefits as: (a) Renewable Energy Generation: Generating electricity using bifacial PV panels to reduce dependency on external energy sources. (b) Thermal and Acoustic Comfort: Improving building performance by reducing heat gain in summer and retaining warmth in winter. (c) Biodiversity Enhancement: Creating a biotope for plants and animals, contributing to urban ecological resilience.

Risks: (a) Structural Compatibility: Ensuring the roof can support the additional load of green roof components and PV panels. (b) Maintenance Accessibility: Maintaining ease of access to critical technical equipment and roof installations. (c) Funding and Timeline: Managing budget constraints and aligning renovation phases with the main ACE retrofit schedule.

3.4.1.1 B2-PV Panels

The PV Panels initiative is a key component of the Brussels Living Lab, focused on enhancing renewable energy generation through the integration of photovoltaic systems. Managed by ACE, this initiative aims to install PV panels with an estimated capacity of 33 kWp. The panels will be strategically placed to maximize energy capture while contributing to the overall energy performance goals of the ACE building. This initiative plays a critical role in achieving the Brussels LL's objective of reducing carbon emissions and fostering energy efficiency.

Technical Features: The PV Panels initiative includes advanced design and implementation phases: (a) Selection of PV Panel Technology: Ensuring high-performance panels with an emphasis on durability and efficiency. (b) Strategic Installation: Placement on the ACE building's

roof to optimize solar exposure and energy production. (c) Energy Management Integration: Connecting the PV system to the building’s Energy Management System (EMS) to monitor and optimize energy flow.

The PV panels installation also includes a comprehensive procurement process to acquire suitable PV technology, followed by detailed installation and commissioning phases. The panels are designed to be compatible with the existing infrastructure and will connect to a local Renewable Energy Community to redistribute surplus energy, especially during off-peak periods such as weekends and holidays.

Key Functionalities: The PV Panels initiative supports several key functionalities: (a) Renewable Energy Generation: Produces clean electricity to meet the building’s operational needs, reducing reliance on grid power. (b) Energy Redistribution: Feeds surplus energy into the Renewable Energy Community, increasing the energy-saving potential of the initiative. (c) Contribution to GBN Goals: Aligns with the broader objectives of the Green Building Neighbourhood (GBN) framework by promoting sustainable energy practices.

Risks: (a) Installation Constraints: Managing structural and logistical challenges during the installation phase. (b) Efficiency Optimization: Ensuring maximum energy production despite potential shading or weather-related issues. (c) Integration Challenges: Seamlessly connecting the PV system to the EMS and other building systems to ensure smooth operation.

Figure 49: Utilities and sensors for measurements and monitoring.

3.4.1.2 B3 – Energy Monitoring System

The Energy Monitoring System activity, led by TPF, focuses on improving energy management at the ACE building by deploying a comprehensive suite of sensors and data collection tools. This initiative seeks to monitor and optimize electricity, gas, and water consumption while improving

Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ). By leveraging real-time data and integrating it with the Demand and Response (D&R) platform, this initiative aims to enhance energy efficiency and promote sustainable behaviour among building users. Figure 49 shows the gas and electric utilities and sensors installation.

Technical Features: The Energy Monitoring System integrates state-of-the-art technologies to monitor and manage energy use: (a) Smart Utility Meters, installed to track electricity and gas consumption with high accuracy, (b) Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) Sensors, measuring parameters such as CO2 levels, humidity, temperature, and window/door openings to assess and improve occupant comfort, and (c) Data Integration with the Demand and Response Platform, enabling real-time energy optimization and decision-making. The installation includes two gas meters, six electricity meters, and multiple sensors for IEQ, all connected through IoT gateways and data management systems.

Key Functionalities: The Energy Monitoring System provides several benefits: (a) Real-Time Energy Monitoring, offering a clear vision of energy consumption to improve energy management and reduce waste, (b) IEQ Enhancement, ensuring better indoor air quality and thermal comfort for building occupants, and (c) Decision Support, utilizing the collected data to inform future energy-saving interventions and assess the effectiveness of renovations.

Risks: (a) Data Accuracy, ensuring the sensors and meters provide reliable and consistent readings, (b) Data governance and privacy for all measurements shared to the Data Space (c) System Integration, addressing potential challenges in linking the monitoring tools with the Demand and Response platform, and (d) Maintenance, managing the long-term upkeep of the monitoring infrastructure.

3.4.1.3 B4 – Social Innovations (IEQ Study)

The Social Innovations initiative, led by SIM, focuses on improving Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) through innovative interventions and comprehensive behavioural studies. This initiative integrates technology, data analysis, and community engagement to enhance building environments and promote sustainability. By assessing and addressing factors such as air quality, thermal comfort, and user behaviour, this project aims to create healthier, more comfortable, and energy-efficient indoor spaces. The sensors for IEQ are implemented in 2

classrooms with important sun exposure (rooms 6B and 4C) and 2 others to the rear of the building with less sun exposure (rooms 3B and 2B), so darker and colder (Figure 50).

Figure 50: Sensors locations for IEQ monitoring.

Technical Features: The IEQ Study employs advanced tools and methodologies to monitor and improve building conditions: (a) IoT Sensors, installed to track key parameters such as CO2 levels, temperature, humidity, and air quality in real-time, (b) Behavioural Data Collection, utilizing sensors to observe door and window usage to analyse user interaction with the building environment, and (c) Intervention Planning and Implementation, conducting seasonal interventions to test and evaluate changes in indoor environmental quality. The data collected is integrated into the project's monitoring platform for detailed analysis and feedback.

Outcomes: The Social Innovations initiative delivers several benefits: (a) Improved Air Quality, addressing issues related to CO2 concentration and biological allergens for healthier indoor environments, (b) Enhanced Thermal Comfort, optimizing temperature and humidity levels to ensure a pleasant atmosphere for building users, and (c) Behavioural Insights, using data-driven methods to inform user engagement strategies and promote sustainable behaviours.

Risks: (a) Sensor Accuracy, ensuring the reliability and precision of data collected through IoT devices, (b) User Engagement, maintaining consistent participation and cooperation from building occupants, and (c) Integration Challenges, linking IEQ monitoring systems with other building management and energy platforms.

3.4.2 Brussels LL Change Management

The Brussels Living Lab is considering replacing the Highly Evaporative Green Roof technology with a Green Roof combined with Solar Panels due to technical challenges related to regulatory compliance. A detailed justification for this change is being prepared. Implementation delays have been caused by constraints with SOP subcontractors, who can only carry out the

installation during school vacation periods. As anticipated, this year's window has passed, making summer 2025 the likely timeframe for implementation. The revised Green Roof design will retain evaporative properties while incorporating an additional 205 square meters of photovoltaic panels, providing a power capacity of 33 kWp, thereby enhancing the energy efficiency and sustainability of the action.

3.4.3 Brussels LL methodology-based mapping

3.4.3.1 Innovations Mapping and KPIs

The ArchiMate schematic of ArchiMate design in Figure 51 shows an overall view of the innovations, the related locations of their testing and the main facilitators of those innovations, as described in section 3.4.1.

Figure 51: Brussels LL innovations development

Each innovation installation and testing activity in the Living Lab (e.g. B1-Green roof) is linked with the main stakeholder (e.g. SOP), the location (e.g. LL4-ACE School), and the related asset which is the output of the work of an innovation related WP (e.g. 3a4. Evaporative Green Roof

/ Walls). The diagram also provides information about the related PROBONO Milestone where each innovation installation is expected to be completed.

Behind all those artifacts which have been given semantic meaning according to ArchiMate methodology, there is a complete model, which connects the different semantic element levels of the methodology, i.e. Motivation, Strategy, Business, Application, Technology and Implementation and Migration layers).

Figure 52 shows the list of KPIs that LL Brussels will be monitoring, in collaboration with WP6 (see Deliverable D6.x, and specifically D6.4).

Figure 52: Brussels LL KPIs

3.4.3.2 Brussels LL Use cases and Data

The Brussels Living Lab (LL4) leverages Digital Twin (DT) technology to address key challenges in energy management, community engagement, and sustainable mobility. These initiatives aim to optimize resource usage, foster collaboration within energy communities, and improve the

Figure 54: Brussels LL Use Cases Datasets

Figure 53: Brussels LL Use Cases

quality of life for inhabitants through safer and greener urban designs. The Living Lab use cases (Figure 53 shows the top-level use cases diagram, and Figure 54 shows the datasets related to those use cases as identified in task T5.1), are centred around three key high-level areas, in the context of the Living Lab.

A. Monitor, Manage, and Optimize Living Lab Energy Systems (BRU-A): Focuses on equipping the Living Lab with advanced tools to monitor, manage, and optimize energy systems. A comprehensive operational dashboard, powered by Digital Twin technology, provides real-time insights into energy performance, allowing stakeholders to identify inefficiencies, anomalies, and opportunities for improvement. By aligning the built environment's energy behaviour with benchmarks, the system ensures optimal performance, reduced energy waste, and lower emissions. It features (a) advanced anomaly detection, energy and production anomalies (e.g., faulty thermostats or misaligned PV panels) are promptly flagged, enabling timely corrective actions, (b) Predictive modelling, where energy consumption patterns are forecasted based on historical data, environmental conditions, and school activity schedules, enabling proactive management, and (c) Comprehensive system insights, with energy usage across electricity, gas, and heat/cold networks.

Use Cases: (BRU-A-UC1) Detect consumption anomalies, (BRU-A-UC2) Detect production anomalies, and (BRU-A-UC3) Build energy models for school equipment usage.

B. Provide a Hosting Platform for the GBN Energy Community (BRU-B): Energy management expanded to neighbourhood, fostering a connected Green Building Neighbourhood (GBN) Energy Community. By acting as a one-stop platform, the DT enables information sharing, collaboration, and optimization within the energy community. The platform also supports the interconnection of multiple GBNs, creating a robust system of systems. Features (a) information sharing and benchmarks, (b) access to best practices, benchmarks, and tools for energy management and decision-making, (c) financial insights, to evaluate the ROI for energy upgrades and monitor long-term impact, (d) decision support with serious games and scenario simulations empower users to test energy policies.

Use Cases: (BRU-B-UC1) information platform to the energy community, (BRU-B-UC2) demonstrate financial returns on investments, (BRU-B-UC3) produce policy impacts through serious games, (BRU-B-UC4) interconnect multiple DTs across GBNs for large-scale optimization.

C. Evaluate GBN Evolution and New Designs in Terms of Mobility (BRU-C): The transformation of mobility systems within the GBN, focusing on improving safety, air quality, and accessibility. The DT simulates mobility scenarios, evaluating their impact on the quality of life for inhabitants and identifying optimal transportation solutions. Features (a) mobility models that integrate GIS data, demographics, and transportation infrastructure for detailed scenario analysis, (b) impact assessment of air quality, CO2 emissions, travel times, and safety for pedestrians and cyclists,

(c) interactive simulations for stakeholders to explore the effects of mobility interventions, such as pedestrian streets and optimized public transport.

Use Cases: (BRU-C-UC1) Find the best mobility scenarios and evaluate their impacts.

3.4.4 Brussels LL Stakeholders

The current organizational structure of the Brussels Living Lab (LL4), focusing on key actors and their primary responsibilities is given in Table 6.

Primary Stakeholders and Roles		
Organization	Category	Primary Responsibilities
De l'Autre Côté de l'Ecole (ACE)	Living Lab Main Stakeholder	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hosts the Brussels LL at ACE school - Manages green roof installation and IEQ monitoring initiatives - Coordinates renovation and stakeholder engagement for Green Neighbourhood initiatives
SOPREMA (SOP)	Technology Provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supplies and installs the Highly Evaporative Green Roof (HEGR) - Provides technical analysis and recommendations - Conducts insulation and waterproofing analysis
STAM	Technology Provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develops the Demand Response Platform - Integrates energy optimization at building and neighbourhood levels
TPF	Technology Provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provides energy metering and monitoring solutions - Supports the Demand Response Platform - Conducts energy performance analysis
TSRV	Technology Provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supplies Smart IoT gateway for energy monitoring
CARTIF	Research Partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analyses data and KPIs for monitoring and optimization
SIN	Research Partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Designs and evaluates social and behavioural innovation strategies for IEQ improvement
VIAS Institute	Research Partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Leads mobility and collaborative engagement studies
COWI	Technology Consultant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provides NovaDM analysis for advanced design evaluation of green roof - Supplies prefabricated concrete solutions for ACE renovations
Anerdgy (ANE)	Energy Consultant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conducts technical analysis for green roof and energy improvements
Supporting Stakeholders		
Organization	Category	Role
Freinet Pedagogy Community	Internal Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Influences the design and functionality of renovations at ACE

Commune of Auderghem	Local Government	- Engages the neighbourhood in Green Building Neighbourhood (GBN) initiatives - Facilitates community engagement - Supports local implementation
Fédération Wallonie-Bruxelles	Funding Source	- Provides funding support for construction works related to education
Community Members and Neighbours	Community Stakeholders	- Engage in co-creation and knowledge sharing for sustainability
End Users and Beneficiaries		
Stakeholder Group	Description	Interaction Type
ACE Students and Teachers	School occupants	- Primary users of improved indoor environmental quality (IEQ) - Beneficiaries of renovated learning spaces
Local Community	Residents of Auderghem	- Participants in neighborhood engagement activities related to GBN - Participants in sustainability and mobility initiatives

Table 6: Brussels LL Stakeholders

3.5 LL5 Aarhus

Figure 55: Aarhus LL Gantt Chart, M25-M60

3.5.1 Aarhus LL Technologies Deployment

The Aarhus Living Lab (LL5) serves as a platform for implementing and testing innovative approaches to sustainable construction, energy storage, promoting human-centred social values, and community engagement. Situated at Campus Viborg and the main campus of Aarhus University, LL5 focuses on integrating flow battery systems and upcycled building designs into its operations to reduce environmental impact, boost the social qualities in buildings, and enhance energy efficiency. Using advanced digital tools such as Digital Twin (DT) technology and human-centred design frameworks (ProBIM), LL5 aims to optimize renovation strategies and building performance. In addition, this Living Lab emphasizes participatory methods, leveraging social innovation tools to engage stakeholders and foster sustainable behaviours within the campus and local community, in addition to efforts for standardising the digitalisation of social value in BIM models together with DIN. Figure 55 shows the Aarhus LL Gantt Chart, for all innovations deployed in the Living Lab and listed in the following.

3.5.1.0 A1-Flow Batteries

The installation of flow batteries (VISB) at Campus Viborg aims to reduce environmental impact, lower life cycle costs, and improve energy supply security. These vanadium redox flow batteries (standart modules with capacity of 40 kWh and 10 kW power output) serve as an energy storage solution that minimizes reliance on expensive grid electricity, often linked to high environmental impact. By storing excess renewable energy generated from on-site PV panels or purchasing low-impact grid energy during off-peak periods, the system enhances energy efficiency and sustainability.

Technical Features: The Flow Battery system incorporates advanced storage and operational technologies: (a) Battery Deployment, covering the procurement, delivery, and installation of flow batteries to meet the energy storage needs of the Aarhus LL, and (b) Data Collection and Monitoring, enabling real-time performance tracking and operational optimization through advanced sensors and monitoring tools.

The initiative involves signing contracts for the purchase of flow batteries, followed by their delivery and installation. Sensor systems that are already built into the battery units will be used to collect data on battery performance, and operational KPIs will be evaluated to ensure optimal functionality. The operational phase will include performance monitoring to maximize the system's efficiency and reliability. VISB flow batteries are designed with a long operational life of 20 years or 20,000 cycles, making them more cost-effective than lithium batteries due to

lower operational and replacement costs. The technology uses two tanks containing a vanadium electrolyte solution, a steel cabinet with control electronics, and a stack where redox reactions occur. Cross-contamination between the electrolytes can slightly reduce efficiency but does not result in resource loss since up to 99% of the electrolyte can be reused in new batteries.

Implementing the batteries requires capacity estimation based on usage data. For new buildings, data from similarly sized structures is being used as a reference. A challenge for the BSS building in University City was finding sufficient physical space for installation due to its highly optimized design. While the batteries require space for water tanks, the installation process itself remains straightforward. Local regulations discourage transporting stored power to other sites due to grid taxation, making on-site energy use more economical. As a result, separate battery systems for Campus Viborg and University City were considered to maximize efficiency and cost-effectiveness. Aarhus University (as clients) have purchased batteries for Campus Viborg (investing university funds by a factor of 2.4 above what was provided by the PROBONO project), and are unlikely to purchase batteries for the main campus due to the issues with having insufficient physical space. A container solution with 60 kW/360 kWh will be delivered in the frame of the project.

A Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) was conducted to evaluate the environmental impact of the battery system from a cradle-to-gate perspective, covering raw material extraction, component production, transport to VISB, and final assembly. The assessment follows ISO standards 14040:2008 and 14044:2008, using Open LCA software and the EcoInvent database. The Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) 3.0 impact assessment method was applied across 28 impact categories, chosen for its comprehensive coverage, EU and global alignment, and customer preferences for reporting perceived environmental friendliness.

Risks: (a) System Integration, ensuring compatibility with existing energy systems and governance frameworks, (b) Data Accuracy, addressing the reliability and accuracy of sensor-collected performance data, and (c) Economic Feasibility, managing the cost-effectiveness of flow battery deployment and long-term operation.

3.5.1.1 A2-Upcycling Renovation Designs

The upcycling designs at Campus Viborg (COWI) aim to minimize both construction activity and environmental impact from a lifecycle perspective. This initiative seeks to minimize waste and reduce the environmental impact of construction by reusing and repurposing building materials in renovation projects. By avoiding demolition and limiting the need for new raw material

extraction, processing, and transport, the approach focuses on sustainability through the reuse of materials and structural elements. Additionally, the site owners emphasize preserving the historical and social value of the campus, formerly an agricultural facility, by repurposing existing structures such as the cattle stable K45. This strategy helps maintain the site's cultural heritage while reducing the overall carbon footprint.

Technical Features and approach: The primary case study is the K45 renovation, which will serve as a model for upcycling approaches and stakeholder engagement in sustainable urban development. The K45 building, constructed in 2003 and covering 1,859 m², was originally an unheated cattle stable with minimal insulation, open ventilation, and a raw steel frame construction with a corrugated sheet facade. It lacks heating and features an irregular concrete floor due to previous agricultural use. Despite its current condition, the structural integrity makes it suitable for renovation, with the proposed goal of transforming it into accommodations for 50 people working with farm animals on the campus.

COWI employs NovaDM, a decision-support tool developed by Aarhus University (AU), to explore renovation alternatives and assess upcycling potential using their expertise in Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). NovaDM assists in evaluating renovation scenarios through design space exploration and KPI analysis. For the K45 renovation, COWI has identified several KPIs, focusing primarily on the embedded energy of materials, which will be the central metric presented to Viborg Kommune. The features and applications of NovaDM are further detailed in D5.6 ("GBN Global Decision Support and Optimisation Platform (I)"), while the K45 case study is elaborated in D3.10 ("Building Materials – Upcycling (II)").

A critical aspect of the implementation involves refining the LCA methodology. Consequential LCA has been favoured for its broader and more accurate climate impact evaluation, as it considers long-term consequences rather than just direct impacts. However, the construction industry is still transitioning from attributional LCA, which is more limited in scope, making the shift to consequential LCA not yet market ready. To support future adaptations, the project emphasizes using local climate data, updated building regulations, and enhanced Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) databases over generic data sources. By combining LCA with decision-support tools like NovaDM, and a focus on cultural preservation, the upcycling approach at Campus Viborg balances sustainability, cost-effectiveness, and historical value in a forward-looking renovation strategy.

Risks: (a) Material Availability, ensuring a reliable supply of suitable upcycled materials for renovation projects, (b) Design Compatibility, addressing challenges in incorporating upcycled

materials into existing structures, and (c) Stakeholder Alignment, managing expectations and securing buy-in from all participants in the renovation process.

3.5.1.2 A3-Human Centred Analysis Tools

The Human-Centred Analysis Tools initiative, led by Aarhus University (AU), focuses on integrating human-centric approaches into sustainable building design and operation. By capturing architectural design intentions for achieving social values (i.e. as an elicitation activity), and then subsequently modelling and digitalising these social intentions natively into BIM models, this approach provides a powerful new way of analysing and promoting social values in buildings including occupant experience, accessibility, awareness and other qualities. A primary focus is on the development of ProBIM and Revit plugins to align social and technical aspects of building design, fostering more inclusive and effective solutions.

Technical Features: The initiative employs advanced methodologies and tools for human-centered analysis: (a) Social Intention Analysis, processing and analysing elicited social intentions to inform building designs and operational strategies, (b) ProBIM and Revit Plugin Development, creating software tools that incorporate user behaviour insights into building information modelling (BIM) workflows, and (c) User Interface and Human-Machine Interaction (UI/HMI) Co-Creation, developing intuitive interfaces that enhance user engagement and interaction with building systems. The initiative also includes activities such as stakeholder evaluation workshops, KPI development for ProBIM, and the implementation of SEEDS (Sustainability, Energy Efficiency, and Design Strategies) in BIM models. Operational KPIs will be assessed to measure the effectiveness of these tools in achieving project objectives.

Key Functionalities: The Human-Centred Analysis Tools initiative provides several key benefits: (a) Behavioural Insights, integrating user behaviour and social intentions into building design and operation, (b) Enhanced Decision-Making, enabling data-driven decisions by incorporating stakeholder feedback and behavioural analysis, and (c) Improved User Experience, creating intuitive and user-friendly digital tools that align with stakeholder needs and sustainability goals.

Risks: (a) Data Quality, ensuring the reliability and accuracy of user behaviour and social intention data, (b) Tool Adoption, addressing potential challenges in user adoption and training for the developed tools, and (c) Integration Challenges, ensuring seamless compatibility of ProBIM and Revit plugins with existing BIM workflows and standards.

3.5.1.3 A4-Social Innovations

The Social Innovations, led by SIN, focuses on fostering community engagement, promoting sustainability, and enhancing public awareness through innovative social projects. This initiative integrates participatory approaches and tools such as GeoDesign, CERNA, and Regen-NXT to inspire behavioural changes, support collaborative urban development, and encourage biodiversity and sustainable practices. By involving communities, institutions, and stakeholders, the initiative creates a shared vision for sustainable development within Aarhus Living Lab.

Features: Social Innovations incorporate diverse strategies and methodologies aimed at engaging communities and fostering a collaborative approach to sustainability: (a) GeoDesign: A participatory planning tool used to develop and evaluate sustainable design actions through configuration, public engagement, and review phases. GeoDesign emphasizes collaboration between stakeholders to align design solutions with environmental and social goals. (b) CERNA: The Climate and Energy Related Norms and Awareness (CERNA) survey identifies social and psychological factors that influence energy-related behaviours. The results guide public engagement activities and policy recommendations to promote pro-environmental norms and behaviours. (c) Regen-NXT: A platform for promoting regeneration-focused innovations that integrate environmental actions with public engagement. By connecting stakeholders, Regen-NXT facilitates the adoption of biodiversity and sustainability-focused strategies within the urban domain. The initiative's activities include public engagement workshops, configuration of actions, and iterative reviews for all three tools to ensure they are responsive to the needs of the Aarhus Living Lab community.

Key Functionalities: The Social Innovations initiative provides multiple benefits as; (a) Community Engagement: Encourages active participation from citizens, stakeholders, and institutions to create shared responsibility for sustainability efforts. (b) Educational Impact: Increases awareness and understanding of sustainable practices and biodiversity through interactive tools and activities. (c) Biodiversity and Environmental Enhancement: Promotes the adoption of biodiversity and nature-based solutions to improve the urban environment and foster ecological resilience.

Risks: (a) Stakeholder Engagement: Ensuring consistent participation and alignment among diverse stakeholders to achieve shared goals, (b) Implementation Challenges: Addressing potential barriers in the adoption and integration of innovative tools and approaches within the community, (c) Data Interpretation: Managing the accuracy and relevance of insights generated from tools such as CERNA and GeoDesign to inform actionable strategies.

3.5.1.4 A99-Biogenic Materials

The Biogenic Materials initiative, led by SOP, focused on studying and testing innovative biogenic materials to reduce the environmental impact of construction. This initiative emphasizes the use of natural and upcycled materials, such as wood fibre insulation, to enhance sustainability while maintaining high performance in energy efficiency and building durability. The Aarhus LL aims to explore these materials as part of a broader effort to integrate sustainable practices into construction and renovation projects.

Technical Approach: The initiative incorporates advanced testing and analysis methodologies: (a) Material Selection: Evaluating a range of biogenic materials, including waste-derived products, for their potential to replace traditional materials. (b) Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), analysing the environmental impact of biogenic materials across their life cycle. (c) Prototyping, developing small-scale prototypes to assess material performance in conditions like those in Denmark.

Key Features: The Biogenic Materials initiative provides several benefits as; (a) Reduced Carbon Footprint: Lowers embodied energy and CO2 emissions using sustainable materials. (b) Waste Reduction: Promotes the reuse of by-products and minimizes material waste in construction. (c) Improved Thermal Performance: Achieves high energy efficiency with materials like wood fibre insulation.

3.5.1 Aarhus LL methodology-based mapping

3.5.1.0 Innovations Mapping and KPIs

The ArchiMate schematic of ArchiMate design in Figure 56 shows an overall view of the innovations, the related locations of their testing and the main facilitators of those innovations, as described in section 3.5.1.

Figure 56: Aarhus LL Innovations development

Each innovation installation and testing activity in the Living Lab (e.g. A1-Flow Batteries) is linked with the main stakeholder (e.g. VISB), the location (e.g. LL5-Campus Viborg), and the related asset which is the output of the work of an innovation related WP (e.g. 4e1. Flow Batteries).

Behind all those artifacts which have been given semantic meaning according to ArchiMate methodology, there is a complete model, which connects the different semantic element levels of the methodology, i.e. Motivation, Strategy, Business, Application, Technology and Implementation and Migration layers).

Figure 57 shows the list of KPIs that LL Aarhus will be monitoring, in collaboration with WP6 (see Deliverable D6.x, and specifically D6.4).

Figure 57: Aarhus LL KPIs

3.5.1.1 Aarhus LL use cases and Data

The Aarhus Living Lab (LL5) leverages Digital Twin (DT) technology for sustainable buildings design. These initiatives aim to optimize the design process, with early user feedback based on LCA metrics and “soft” assessment criteria providing early DGNB (German Society for Sustainable Buildings) assessment. The Living Lab use cases (Figure 58 shows the top-level use

cases diagram and the datasets related to those use cases as identified in task T5.1), are centred around two key high-level areas, in the context of this Living Lab.

Figure 58: LL Aarhus DT use cases and datasets

A. Ensure Final Design Meets Criteria for Sustainable Buildings (AAR-A): Ensure the final design of the Kitchen 2.0 and BSS buildings meets stringent criteria for occupant experience, environmental impact, and cost-effectiveness, aligning with DGNB Gold certification standards. Leveraging Digital Twin technology and advanced decision-support tools, the Aarhus Living Lab equips architects and engineers with real-time insights to refine their designs. This approach addresses historical challenges with occupant satisfaction and energy performance in past renovations, ensuring both functional and experiential excellence in the outcome. Key features include: (a) Rapid Feedback on LCA Metrics, providing instant visual feedback on sustainability impacts, identifying critical design elements ("hot spots") and enabling architects to explore alternatives with minimal delay, (b) Human-Centred Design Feedback, with evidence-based assessments of human-centric criteria such as air quality, thermal comfort, and occupant satisfaction allow architects to refine designs based on qualitative and quantitative insights, (c) Collaborative Feedback Loops, where the integration of ProBIM models ensures seamless communication between architects and engineers, enabling early detection and resolution of conflicts between functional and experiential goals, and (d) Automated DGNB Assessment, with systematic sampling of the design space evaluates alternatives against DGNB standards,

clustering configurations for optimal performance across sustainability and occupant well-being metrics.

Use Cases: (AAR-A-UC1) - Provide rapid feedback on LCA metrics at an early design stage. (AAR-A-UC2) - Provide feedback on human-centred "soft" criteria at an early design stage, (AAR-A-UC3) - Provide feedback on human-centred criteria to engineers during design updates and (AAR-A-UC4) - Provide automated DGNB-specific assessment during design space exploration.

B. Generating New Knowledge for Sustainable Design (AAR-B): generate actionable insights by comparing the design-phase predictions for occupant experience, environmental performance, and cost-effectiveness with the real-world data collected during the operational phase. This iterative feedback process validates the rationale to refine future designs for GBN. This informs subsequent renovation stages and capture the knowledge in a process framework that can be applied across the AU Campus 2.0 program. Features: (a) Validation of Design Predictions, to enable continuous assessment of LCA metrics, human-centred criteria, and DGNB indicator scores, ensuring alignment between design goals and operations. (b) Real-Time Feedback Loops, to identify discrepancies between predicted and actual performance, delivering insights to architects, facility managers, and other stakeholders, and (c) Dynamic Operational Optimization, using real-time data and the Digital Twin for flexible reconfiguration of building and energy management systems (BMS & EMS), enhancing occupant experience and environmental performance.

Use Cases: (AAR-B-UC1) design-stage predictions verification when the building is in operation.

3.5.2 Aarhus LL Stakeholders

The current organizational structure of the Aarhus Living Lab (LL5), focusing on key actors and their primary responsibilities is given in Table 7.

Primary Stakeholders and Roles		
Organization	Category	Primary Responsibilities
Aarhus University (AU)	Living Lab Main Stakeholder	- Hosts the Aarhus LL
		- Oversees the implementation of technologies across campus sites
		- Coordinates renovation and stakeholder engagement
		- Manages Campus Viborg renovation projects

VISBLUE	Technology Provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supplies and implements flow batteries - Conducts LCA and cost analysis for battery solutions
COWI	Technology Provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develops upcycling renovation designs for Campus Viborg - Conducts LCA for material reuse and sustainability - Designs upcycling strategies for K45 building - Develops tools for Consequential LCA
ITA INNOVA	Research Partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provides Ventilation Assessment Tool - Develops Comfort Virtual Sensor for air quality and comfort analysis
SOPREMA	Technology Provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supplies biogen construction materials - Offers sustainable insulation solutions
AU Estates	Facility Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manages and oversees construction projects at Campus Viborg - Coordinates renovation projects
AART Architects	Design Partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Designs the Kitchen 2.0 building with human-centred analysis integration - Designs BSS buildings - Integrates DGNB Gold certification criteria
Supporting Stakeholders		
Organization	Category	Role
Viborg Kommune	Local Government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regulates building renovation and new construction - Influences decisions on upcycling versus demolition - Evaluates building permits
NIRAS Engineering Consultancy	External Consultant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supports solar panel and battery analysis - Manages tender processes and implementation
Mott Macdonald	Consultant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provides GBN ambitions assessment for aligning goals and outcomes
End Users and Beneficiaries		
Stakeholder Group	Description	Interaction Type
AU Students and Faculty	University occupants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users of renovated spaces and sustainable technologies - Participants in social and behavioural studies - Beneficiaries of social and environmental improvements
Local Community	Viborg residents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indirect beneficiaries of environmental sustainability and innovation efforts

Table 7: Aarhus Stakeholders

3.6.1 Prague LL Technologies Deployment

Prague Living Lab (LL6) serves as a testbed for implementing and evaluating the PROBONO innovative technologies, to transform the Building B of the Faculty of Civil Engineering at the Czech Technical University (CTU) into a sustainable, energy-positive building. Key focus areas include the deployment of Building-Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV), a hybrid green roof with photovoltaic panels, and advanced systems for optimizing indoor air quality and energy performance. Further, it integrates Digital Twin (DT) technology to monitor and manage energy systems in real time, while Virtual Reality (VR) tools in collaboration with DT, enhance facility management and stakeholder engagement. Through a data-driven approach LL6 addresses critical challenges like energy efficiency, material optimization, and indoor environmental quality, setting a benchmark for sustainable retrofitting and smart urban development. Figure 59 shows the Prague LL Gantt Chart, for all innovations deployed in the Living Lab and listed in the following.

3.6.1.1 PR1 – Building-Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV)

The BIPV initiative for sustainable building design supported by FHRF, demonstrates how innovative photovoltaic technology can enhance both environmental performance and architectural aesthetics, serving as a model for future green building developments. The action focuses on transforming Building B at the Faculty of Civil Engineering of the Czech Technical University in Prague through innovative photovoltaic technology integration. The project aims to convert the building into an energy-positive structure while enhancing its thermal comfort and visual appearance.

Technical Features: The BIPV system incorporates sophisticated elements designed to maximize both energy performance and architectural harmony. The existing aluminium curtain façade will be replaced with a BIPV-integrated system featuring vertical opaque PV panels and horizontal PV shading devices. These panels are positioned on the southern façade, with cantilevered shading devices optimizing solar exposure while reducing summer heat gain. The design includes triple glazing and advanced external roller blinds for enhanced thermal control and occupant comfort.

The system's development is supported by energy production simulations and calculations. The integrated PV panels are designed to generate substantial amounts of renewable energy, contributing directly to the building's operational energy needs. Multiple design scenarios were

prepared during the pre-study phase for flexibility in implementation based on technical and aesthetic considerations.

Key Functionalities: The system generates renewable energy on-site, reducing reliance on grid electricity. The horizontal PV panels serve dual purposes as shading devices, significantly improving the building's thermal performance and reducing operational costs. The design is aesthetically integrated, maintaining architectural integrity while seamlessly integrating energy generation capabilities.

Risks: (a) Financial, where limited retrofit budget may constrain the adoption of advanced BIPV designs, (b) Structural compatibility must be ensured between the existing façade and new BIPV components. (c) Technical challenges include addressing potential efficiency losses from shading or suboptimal panel positioning. For the success of the tenders, it is crucial to incorporate the recommendations and BIPV design scenarios into the contractor's tender documentation remains crucial.

3.6.1.2 PR2 - Green Roof with PV

The Green Roof + PV initiative is a forward-thinking solution developed in tasks T3.2 (SOP) and T4.4 (ANE) to address urban environmental challenges, enhance building performance, and serve as a model for integrating renewable energy and green design in urban contexts. It introduces a hybrid design that combines the benefits of green roofs with photovoltaic (PV) panels to improve building sustainability and environmental performance. This innovation addresses urban challenges by incorporating high-evapotranspiration systems, advanced insulation, and renewable energy generation into the roof structures of buildings. The initiative enhances energy efficiency, biodiversity, urban microclimates, and rainwater management, providing a holistic approach to sustainable building practices.

Technical Features: The initiative integrates multiple design elements and technical solutions to achieve its objectives: (a) an Extensive Green Roof, providing high evapotranspiration properties that improve biodiversity, thermal regulation, and rainwater management, (b) Photovoltaic Integration, with PV panels strategically placed to maximize energy generation while preserving the efficiency and ecological benefits of the green roof, and (c) Enhanced Insulation, incorporating bio-solar components to meet modern energy standards, improve indoor comfort, and support sustainability goals. SOP plays a critical role by providing detailed technical solutions and conducting simulations to assess the impacts of the green roof on both indoor and outdoor microclimates, offering actionable insights to optimize the design.

The Green Roof + PV initiative delivers significant benefits to buildings and urban environments: (a) Biodiversity Enhancement, by creating habitats for flora and fauna and improving urban ecosystems, (b) Rainwater Retention, reducing peak water flow, mitigating urban flooding risks, and supporting effective stormwater management, (c) Energy Savings, achieved by reducing heating and cooling demands through improved insulation and shading, and (d) Renewable Energy Generation, leveraging PV panels to produce sustainable electricity for building operations. These functionalities work together to create energy-efficient and environmentally friendly building solutions, promoting urban sustainability.

Risks: The initiative faces several key risks: (a) Structural Compatibility, ensuring that roof structures can support the additional loads of the green roof and PV panels without compromising safety or functionality, (b) Maintenance Accessibility, maintaining ease of access to essential equipment on the roof for repairs and upkeep, and (c) Integration Challenges, ensuring seamless compatibility between green roof components and energy systems to avoid performance issues or operational inefficiencies. Proper planning and collaboration between stakeholders are essential to address these risks and ensure long-term success.

3.6.1.3 PRO – Energy Positive Building

The Energy Positive Building activity is led by FHRF with contributions from CTU, integrates all energy positive technologies and solutions deployed in Prague LL, and it focuses on designing and implementing building systems that achieve a net-positive energy balance. It integrates innovative technologies, and energy-efficient solutions to create buildings that generate more energy than they consume. By combining renewable energy generation, efficient energy management, and optimized building designs, the “Energy Positive Building” sets a new benchmark for sustainable and energy-positive construction in the Prague LL.

Technical Activities: The task involves: (a) Energy Positive Building Design, led by FHRF, which develops architectural and engineering solutions to maximize energy efficiency and renewable energy generation while maintaining aesthetic and functional quality, (b) Alternative Designs and Evaluation, exploring different configurations and systems to identify the most effective combinations for achieving energy-positive outcomes, and (c) Recommendations to Tender, created by CTU, which outline technical specifications and guidelines to ensure that energy-positive criteria are met during the construction and procurement processes.

Key Features: The Energy Positive Building initiative delivers transformative benefits: (a) Renewable Energy Generation, achieved through the integration of technologies like

photovoltaic panels, energy storage systems, and solar thermal solutions, (b) Energy Efficiency, through optimized building envelopes, advanced HVAC systems, and smart energy management tools, (c) Reduced Environmental Impact, by minimizing operational energy consumption and promoting the use of low-impact building materials, and (d) Economic Savings, resulting from lower energy bills and potential incentives for energy-positive performance.

Risks: (a) Performance Uncertainty, ensuring that design and operational strategies achieve the intended energy-positive outcomes under real-world conditions, (b) Integration Challenges, managing the compatibility of various energy generation and management systems, (c) Cost Implications, balancing the upfront investment in energy-positive technologies with long-term savings and project budgets, and (d) Regulatory Compliance, meeting local and EU standards for energy efficiency, renewable energy, and sustainability.

3.6.1.4 PR3 – Optimal Indoor Air Quality (IAQ)

The Optimal Indoor Air Quality (IAQ) is led by ITA with contributions from CTU, focuses on enhancing the indoor environmental quality of buildings in the Prague Living Lab through innovative design and advanced simulation techniques. The aim is to ensure comfortable, healthy, and energy-efficient indoor environments by optimizing ventilation, air quality, and thermal comfort. It addresses the growing need for sustainable indoor spaces that prioritize occupant well-being while reducing energy demands.

Technical Features: The PR3 initiative involves the development and application of multiple advanced tools and methodologies to improve indoor air quality and thermal comfort. These include (a) a Ventilation and Air Quality Tool developed by ITA, designed to monitor and optimize indoor air conditions by balancing ventilation efficiency with energy consumption, (b) the Simplification of BIM Models by CTU, enabling streamlined design processes and better integration of IAQ optimization measures into building projects, (c) a Preliminary Radiation Model by ITA, which assesses sunlight penetration and its effects on building interiors, and (d) Thermal Comfort and Cooling Demand Simulations, conducted to predict and improve thermal conditions in indoor spaces while minimizing energy usage.

Key Functionalities: The Optimal IAQ initiative provides several crucial benefits: (a) Enhanced Air Quality, achieved through optimized ventilation systems that maintain safe and healthy CO₂ levels and remove pollutants, (b) Improved Thermal Comfort, ensuring pleasant indoor temperatures while balancing energy efficiency, (c) Efficient Design Processes, supported by the integration of simplified BIM models that facilitate the implementation of IAQ measures, and

(d) Energy Optimization, achieved by simulations that identify strategies for reducing cooling demands without compromising occupant comfort.

Risks: The PR3 initiative addresses key risks associated with indoor air quality improvement efforts: (a) Accuracy of Simulations and Models, ensuring that tools like the radiation and thermal comfort simulations deliver reliable results for implementation, (b) Integration Challenges, addressing the complexity of incorporating ventilation and air quality tools into existing systems and designs, and (c) Balancing Energy and IAQ Objectives, managing the trade-offs between maintaining high air quality and minimizing energy consumption.

3.6.1.5 PR4 – Digital Twin (DT)

The Digital Twin (DT) integration led by AKKA with contributions from CTU, CARTIF, KNT, and eBOS, focuses on the development and deployment of a comprehensive digital representation of the Prague Living Lab's built environment. It aims to enhance decision-making, monitoring, and optimization of building performance by leveraging advanced data integration, visualization, and simulation tools. The Digital Twin acts as a dynamic, real-time model that provides actionable insights into building operations and facilitates collaboration among stakeholders.

Technical Features: The DT encompasses multiple innovative elements: (a) KPIs Definition, led by CTU, to guide decision-making and measure the effectiveness of interventions, (b) Benchmarks and Targets for KPIs, aligned to the WP6 developed monitoring framework by CARTIF, (c) APIs Creation, developed by KNT, to enable seamless integration of various data sources and tools into the Digital Twin platform, and (d) an HMI-Dashboard, designed and implemented by eBOS, to provide an intuitive interface for visualizing real-time data, simulating scenarios, and monitoring building performance.

Key Functionalities: The Digital Twin delivers: (a) Enhanced Decision Support, enabling stakeholders to make data-driven decisions based on real-time insights and predictive simulations, (b) Performance Monitoring, providing continuous tracking of energy use, indoor air quality, and other KPIs to optimize building operations, (c) Data Integration, ensuring interoperability between different systems and tools through robust APIs and common data spaces, and (d) Stakeholder Collaboration, facilitating communication and coordination by providing a shared platform for visualizing and analysing building data.

Risks: (a) Data Accuracy and Completeness, ensuring the reliability of data inputs and the consistency of real-time updates within the Digital Twin, (b) System Integration Challenges,

managing the complexity of connecting various data sources and technologies into a unified platform, (c) User Adoption, ensuring that the HMI-Dashboard is intuitive and meets the needs of diverse stakeholders, and (d) Data Privacy and Security, addressing concerns related to the handling and sharing of sensitive building and operational data.

3.6.1.6 PR5 – Virtual Reality (VR)

The Virtual Reality (VR) development is led by CTU and focuses on developing augmented and virtual reality tools to enhance facility management and operational decision-making. The aim is to integrate advanced visualization technologies into building operations, providing stakeholders with immersive and interactive tools to manage and optimize building performance effectively. By leveraging VR, the initiative enhances user engagement, streamlines maintenance processes, and facilitates better understanding of building systems.

Technical Features: Incorporates advanced VR and augmented reality tools to improve facility management. Key features: (a) Augmented Data Facility Management, where building information and operational data are superimposed onto a virtual model of the facility, enabling stakeholders to access real-time data and visualize system performance in an interactive environment. Incorporate 3D modelling of building systems to enhance the understanding of spatial and functional relationships, and (b) Scenario Simulation, allowing stakeholders to test various operational strategies, maintenance schedules, and performance improvements in a virtual environment before implementing them in real-world scenarios.

Key Functionalities: The Virtual Reality component delivers: (a) Enhanced Visualization, providing an immersive and intuitive understanding of complex building systems, enabling stakeholders to quickly identify issues and optimize operations, (b) Streamlined Maintenance, allowing facility managers to visualize building components and plan maintenance activities with greater accuracy and efficiency, (c) Improved Decision-Making, through real-time data integration and simulation tools that support predictive and proactive management strategies, and (d) User Training and Collaboration, creating a virtual environment for training personnel and fostering collaboration among diverse stakeholders.

Risks: (a) Technological Complexity, ensuring the VR tools are reliable and user-friendly for stakeholders with varying levels of technical expertise, (b) Data Integration Challenges, managing the seamless incorporation of operational data into the virtual models, (c) Hardware and Software Compatibility, ensuring the VR solutions are accessible across different devices and the DT.

3.6.2 Prague LL methodology-based mapping

3.6.2.0 Innovations Mapping and KPIs

The ArchiMate schematic of ArchiMate design in Figure 60 shows an overall view of the innovations, the related locations of their testing and the main facilitators of those innovations, as described in section 0.

Each innovation installation and testing activity in the Living Lab (e.g. PR3-Optimal IAQ) is linked with the main stakeholder (e.g. ITA), the location (e.g. LL6-Building B), and the related asset which is the output of the work of an innovation related WP (e.g. 4a1. Planning SW for optimal energy systems design).

Behind all those artifacts which have been given semantic meaning according to ArchiMate methodology, there is a complete model, which connects the different semantic element levels of the methodology, i.e. Motivation, Strategy, Business, Application, Technology and Implementation and Migration layers).

Figure 60: LL Prague Innovations

Figure 61 shows the list of KPIs that LL Aarhus will be monitoring, in collaboration with WP6 (see Deliverable D6.x, and specifically

Figure 61: Prague LL KPIs

3.6.2.1 Prague LL use cases and Data

The Prague Living Lab (LL6) employs Digital Twin (DT) technology to optimize energy management and sustainable retrofitting. By unifying data on electricity, heat, and internal climate, the DT provides a comprehensive view of system interactions. It supports informed decision-making for building exploitation and evaluates retrofit designs to improve energy efficiency and reduce environmental impact. The Living Lab use cases (Figure 62 shows the top-

level use cases diagram and the datasets related to those use cases as identified in task T5.1), are centred around two key high-level areas, in the context of this Living Lab.

Figure 62: Prague LL use cases and datasets

A. Monitor and Manage Energy Systems (PRG-A): Optimises energy management of Building B by providing a unified view of electricity consumption, production, heat flow, and internal climate. The DT consolidates all energy data into a single platform, allowing stuff to monitor and to simulate energy interactions in real-time. Features: (a) Energy Flow Monitoring, where the DT provides detailed insights into electricity and heat flows, including production and consumption dynamics across the GBN, ensuring efficient resource utilization, detailing each device's power usage. It monitors key systems, including rooftop solar panels, south façade production units, HVAC systems, lighting, elevators, and e-mobility charging stations. The DT also visualizes electricity exchanges between Building B and other GBN buildings, integrating agrivoltaics

contributions. Internal (b) Climate Visualization, where the system monitors and displays dynamic internal climate parameters such as temperature, humidity, and air quality, offering a holistic view of building performance, (c) Performance Issue Detection, where the DT identifies anomalies by comparing real-world data with simulation results, flagging underperforming equipment or systems to alert the technical team for prompt corrective actions.

Use Cases: (PRG-A-UC1) Monitor electricity consumption and flow, (PRG-A-UC2) Monitor electricity production units, (PRG-A-UC3) Monitor air flow and internal climate, and (PRG-A-UC4) Detect performance issues and alert the technical team.

B. Design and Material Choice for Building B Retrofit (PRG-B): supports the selection of optimal materials and designs for retrofitting Building B, focusing on evaluating their impact on the entire GBN over its lifecycle. The DT simulates various design configurations, analysing energy performance, internal climate conditions, and lifecycle CO₂ emissions. The insights enable the project team to make data-driven decisions for sustainable retrofitting. Features: (a) Scenario-Based Design Evaluation, where the DT tests multiple hypotheses for roof and southern façade configurations, including varying solar panel angles and material usage, to assess their impact on energy production and insulation. (b) Lifecycle Impact Assessment, where the DT calculates CO₂ emissions and energy performance across the building's lifecycle, considering material production, retrofit workshops, and daily operations, and (c) Dynamic Interaction Modelling, to forecast energy surplus and deficit periods within Building B, highlighting interactions with other GBN components, such as agrivoltaics and adjacent buildings.

Use Case: (PRG-B-UC1) Evaluate different roof and south façade designs.

3.6.3 Prague LL Stakeholders

The current organizational structure of the Prague Living Lab (LL6), focusing on key actors and their primary responsibilities is given in Table 8.

Primary Stakeholders and Roles		
Organization	Category	Primary Responsibilities
Czech Technical University (CTU)	Main LL stakeholder	- Hosts the Prague LL
		- Leads the revitalization of Building B
		- Oversees planning, management, and funding acquisition
Prague 6 Municipal Authority	Local Government	- Provides local / regional support for the revitalization
		- Regulates buildings and urban planning

		- Oversees construction regulations
Fraunhofer ISE (FRHF)	Technology Provider	- Designs energy-efficient building envelope - Develops Energy Positive Building concepts - Implements energy-positive building technologies
ANERDGY (ANE)	Technology Provider	- Develops conceptual design for bio-solar roofs
SOPREMA (SOP)	Technology Provider	- Provides technical solutions for bio-solar roofs - Implements insulation innovations - Develops green roof systems
Instituto Tecnológico de Aragón (ITA)	Research Partner	- Develops CFD software models and solutions (OpenFOAM) for ventilation assessment - Provides thermal comfort and air quality tools
Konnecta (KNT)	Technology Provider	- Develops API and data collection systems for the Digital Twin
EBOS Technologies Limited (eBOS)	Technology Provider	- Develops Human-Machine Interface for KPI visualization
Fundación CARTIF (CARTIF)	Research Partner	- Defines KPIs and develops monitoring systems - Conducts evaluation of implemented solutions
AKKA High Tech (AKKA)	Technology Provider	- Deploys the Digital Twin for energy and resource monitoring
Supporting Stakeholders		
Organization	Category	Role
Czech Technical University Rectorate	Management Body	- Coordinates internal funding approval from deans - Secures faculty funding approval
Ministry of Education	Government Agency	- Provides subsidy funding for the revitalization project
Local Contractors	Implementation Partner	- Participate in tendering and construction processes
End Users and Beneficiaries		
Stakeholder Group	Description	Interaction Type
CTU Students and Faculty	University occupants	- Beneficiaries of revitalized Building B - Users of Digital Twin for education and facility management
Prague Local Community	Residents of Prague 6	- Indirect beneficiaries of improved urban and building sustainability

Table 8: Prague Stakeholders

4 Living Labs Projects Consolidation and analysis

4.1 Technology Profiles of the Living Labs

This report provides for every living lab the set of initiatives being implemented. These initiatives may be categorised according to their related impact, to initiatives for: (a) Energy Performance and Sustainability, (b) Resource Efficiency and Lifecycle Optimization, (c) Scalability and Replicability, and (d) User-Centric Quality Improvements. For instance: the (a) Energy Performance and Sustainability focuses on impacts related to emissions reduction (I1) and energy efficiency (I3), the (b) Resource Efficiency and Lifecycle Optimization directly supports impacts related to reducing embodied energy (I6) and lifecycle costs (I5), the (c) Scalability and Replicability addresses high-potential replication and market uptake (I8, I9) and the (d) User-Centric Quality Improvements targets indoor environmental quality (I10) and social acceptance (I4). Such classification as also explained in the methodology section 2, enables e.g. to sketch a more focused set of related activities and the adoption and deployment of specific technologies and solutions (Table 9).

The flagship Living Labs, Dublin (LL1) and Madrid (LL2), demonstrate broad, integrated portfolios of innovations across all clusters. Dublin mainly focuses Energy Performance and Sustainability, with initiatives driving energy efficiency and smart energy management. Madrid significantly contributes to Resource Efficiency and Lifecycle Optimization, with the Low Carbon Concrete (M1) and Geothermal DHC Network (M12), towards circular economy principles and renewable energy integration.

Cluster	Energy Performance and Sustainability	Resource Efficiency and Lifecycle Optimization	Scalability and Replicability	User-Centric Quality Improvements
Impacts	I1, I4, I5, I7	I2, I6, I9	I3, I8	I10
Key Themes	Energy efficiency, emissions reduction, air quality, and achieving near-zero/positive energy performance.	Reducing embodied energy, lifecycle costs, construction time, and driving investments in sustainable energy.	Demonstration of innovative solutions that exceed current standards and establishing high replicability.	Enhancing indoor environmental quality, occupant well-being, and retrofitting processes for better outcomes.
Dublin (LL1)	D1-Hybrid Green Roof, D2-Photovoltaic System (BAPV), D7-Digital Twin,	D1-Hybrid Green Roof, D4-Battery Bank, D8-Insulation	D7-Digital Twin, D6-Energy Trading Platform, D3-	D9-Social Innovations, D8-Insulation

	D4-Battery Bank, D6-Energy Trading Platform, D3-Photovoltaic System (BIPV)		Photovoltaic System (BIPV), D9-Social Innovations, D1-Hybrid Green Roof	
Madrid (LL2)	M12-Geothermal DHC Network, M8-Digital Twin for DHC Network, M11-Geothermal Heat Pump, M5-Second Life Batteries	M1-Low Carbon Concrete, M7-Model Demolition, M2-Low Carbon Asphalt, M6-Model Material Movements, M3-Reclaimed Insulation	M8-Digital Twin for DHC Network, M12-Geothermal DHC Network, M10-Heat Island Effect Model, M13-Social Innovations, M4-Electric Vehicles	M13-Social Innovations, M9-Digital Twin for Environmental Impact, M3-Reclaimed Insulation
Porto (LL3)	P1-Cool Roof with Bifacial PV, P2-Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G), P3-Solar-to-Vehicle (S2V), P4-Building-Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV), P6-Second Life Batteries, P7-Smart EV Hub (SEVH), P5-Renewable Energy Community (REC)	P1-Cool Roof with Bifacial PV, P6-Second Life Batteries, P8-Phase Change Materials (PCMs)	P5-Renewable Energy Community, P7-Smart Energy Virtual Hub (SEVH), P10-Social Innovations, P3-Solar-to-Vehicle	P10-Social Innovations, P9- Inform Users About Energy Use
Brussels (LL4)	B1-Cool Roof with Bifacial PV, B2-PV Panels, B3-Energy Monitoring System	B3-Energy Monitoring System, B1-Cool Roof with Bifacial PV	B4-Social Innovations, B2-PV Panels, B3-Energy Monitoring System, B1-Cool Roof with Bifacial PV	B4-Social Innovations (IEQ Study)
Aarhus (LL5)	A1-Flow Batteries, A3-Human Centred Analysis Tools, A99-Biogenic Materials	A99-Biogenic Materials, A2-Upcycling Renovation Designs, A3-Human Centred Analysis Tools	A3-Human Centred Analysis Tools, A4-Social Innovations, A2-Upcycling Renovation Designs	A3-Human-Centred Analysis Tools, A4-Social Innovations, A99-Biogenic Materials
Prague (LL6)	PR4-Digital Twin, PR1-Photovoltaic System (BIPV), PR2-Green Roof with PV	PR2-Green Roof with PV, PR4-Digital Twin, PR3-Optimal Indoor Air Quality (IAQ)	PR4-Digital Twin for Energy Management, PR5-Virtual Reality, PR1-Photovoltaic System (BIPV)	PR5-Virtual Reality, PR3-Optimal Indoor Air Quality (IAQ)

Table 9: Living Labs initiatives clusters

Porto (LL3) focuses on Energy Performance and Sustainability and Scalability and Replicability, demonstrating cutting-edge solutions for renewable energy and mobility. Brussels (LL4) focuses on monitoring systems for energy consumption, renewable use of energy and resources efficiency, also to indoor air quality. Aarhus (LL5) emphasizes in human-centred analysis tools for user centric improvements of life quality, and Prague (LL6) leverages PROBONO to achieve investments in Green Buildings and Neighbourhoods, with a big tender development for large-scale sustainable urban solutions.

4.2 Linking Living Labs initiatives to ISO 37100

As highlighted in Deliverable D9.8 about the standardisation activities within PROBONO, the standards series ISO37100 supports the GBN concept, dealing with smart sustainable communities, providing a common approach between the conceptualisation of communities and the methods and tools of management systems. The ISO 37100 series provides a robust framework for cities and communities to achieve sustainable development by integrating environmental, social, and economic considerations, helping to identify and to plan for improving essential urban services, ensuring they contribute to long-term sustainability goals, thereby letting cities enhance their resilience, inclusivity, and overall quality of life for their residents.

The same has also been highlighted in Deliverable D1.4 on the “Strategic Vision and KPI Formulation” of PROBONO, noting that ISO 37101 provides a sound platform for the analysis of GBN targeting initiatives, as it involves for a palette of (twelve) sustainable initiatives such as: (1) Governance, Empowerment and Engagement, (2) Education and Capacity Building, (3) Innovation, Creativity and Research, (4) Health and Care in the Community, (5) Culture and Community Identity, (6) Living Together, Interdependence and Mutuality, (7) Economy and Sustainable Production and Consumption, (8) Living and Working Environment, (9) Safety and Security, (10) Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, (11) Community and Smart Infrastructures and (12) Mobility. Upon the definition of those initiatives the optimal six (6) characteristics that promote sustainability are: (a) Attractiveness, (b) Preservation and Improvement of Environment, (c) Resilience, (d) Responsible Resource Use, (e) Social Cohesion, (f) Well-being,

In the following paragraphs, a first approach of mapping the Living Labs initiatives of PROBONO upon the ISO371xx framework is presented. This mapping will continue in collaboration with work-packages WP1 and WP9.

4.2.1 LL1 - Dublin

Innovation	Relevant ISO 37100 Services	Sustainability Features	Relevance
D1-Hybrid Green Roof	Living & Working Environment, Biodiversity & Ecosystem Services	Preservation & Improvement of Environment, Social Cohesion	The green roof enhances urban cooling, biodiversity, and stormwater management while promoting community well-being.
D2-Photovoltaic	Community Smart Infrastructures, Economy &	Responsible Resource Use, Resilience	BAPV reduces dependence on fossil fuels and integrates with the smart grid,

System (BAPV)	Sustainable Production		providing a low-cost renewable energy source.
D3-Photovoltaic System (BIPV)	Community Smart Infrastructures, Living & Working Environment	Attractiveness, Responsible Resource Use	BIPV blends energy generation into building facades, supporting aesthetic integration and grid decentralization.
D4-Battery Bank	Safety & Security, Economy & Sustainable Production	Resilience, Responsible Resource Use	Provides backup power, load balancing, and enables efficient energy storage, ensuring grid stability.
D5-2-Way EV Chargers	Mobility, Energy Trading & Management	Responsible Resource Use, Resilience	Enables Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) interactions, optimizing renewable energy use and supporting smart mobility.
D6-Energy Trading Platform	Community Smart Infrastructures, Living Together & Mutuality	Resilience, Responsible Resource Use	Empowers peer-to-peer energy transactions, enhancing energy equity and supporting a decentralized energy market.
D7-Digital Twin	Governance, Smart City Planning, Community Smart Infrastructures	Resilience, Preservation & Improvement of Environment	Provides real-time data analytics for energy forecasting, urban planning, and predictive maintenance.
D8-Insulation	Health & Care in the Community, Living & Working Environment	Well-being, Preservation & Improvement of Environment	Reduces energy demand, improves indoor air quality, and supports heritage building retrofits.
D9-Social Innovations	Governance & Engagement, Education & Capacity Building	Social Cohesion, Well-being	Involves GeoDesign workshops, post-occupancy evaluations, and Open House events to engage citizens in sustainability initiatives.

Table 10: Dublin LL Initiatives ISO37100 mapping

4.2.2 LL2 - Madrid

Innovation	Relevant ISO 37100 Services	Sustainability Features	Relevance
M1-Low Carbon Concrete	Economy & Sustainable Production, Living & Working Environment	Responsible Resource Use, Preservation & Improvement of Environment	Uses recycled and industrial by-products to reduce embodied carbon, ensuring compliance with Spanish Structural Code (RD 470/2021).
M2-Low Carbon Asphalt	Community Smart Infrastructures, Mobility	Resilience, Responsible Resource Use	Integrates reclaimed asphalt and supplementary cementitious materials, reducing CO ₂ emissions while maintaining road durability.
M3-Reclaimed Insulation	Health & Care in the Community, Economy & Sustainable Production	Well-being, Responsible Resource Use	Utilizes low-recyclability plastic waste in high-performance insulation, reducing energy demand and improving thermal comfort.
M4-Electric Vehicles	Mobility, Community Smart Infrastructures	Responsible Resource Use, Resilience	Implements bidirectional EV chargers with V2G technology, supporting renewable energy use and optimizing grid balance.
M5-2nd Life Batteries	Safety & Security, Community Smart Infrastructures	Resilience, Responsible Resource Use	Repurposes EV lithium-ion batteries for stationary energy storage, reducing environmental impact while enhancing energy resilience.
M6-Model Material Movements	Economy & Sustainable Production,	Preservation & Improvement of Environment,	Uses GIS-based tracking and real-time logistics modelling to reduce transport emissions and optimize material reuse.

	Governance & Engagement	Responsible Resource Use	
M7-Model Demolition Existing Building	Community Smart Infrastructures, Biodiversity & Ecosystem Services	Responsible Resource Use, Resilience	Supports circular economy principles by cataloguing and reusing demolition materials, reducing landfill waste.
M8-DT for DHC Network	Community Smart Infrastructures, Governance & Engagement	Resilience, Preservation & Improvement of Environment	Provides real-time monitoring and energy flow optimization for the Geothermal DHC system, improving operational efficiency.
M9-DT Reduce Environmental Impact	Governance & Engagement, Biodiversity & Ecosystem Services	Resilience, Preservation & Improvement of Environment	Enables real-time monitoring of pollutant emissions, supporting data-driven environmental decisions.
M10-DT Heat Island Effect Model	Community Smart Infrastructures, Living & Working Environment	Resilience, Well-being	Uses high-resolution satellite data and climate models to predict and mitigate urban heat islands.
M11-Geothermal Heat Pump	Community Smart Infrastructures, Energy Services	Responsible Resource Use, Preservation & Improvement of Environment	Provides zero-emission heating and cooling, reducing reliance on fossil fuels while maximizing geothermal efficiency.
M12-Geothermal DHC Network	Community Smart Infrastructures, Economy & Sustainable Production	Responsible Resource Use, Resilience	Supports a low-carbon energy system for heating and cooling, reducing GHG emissions and operational costs.
M13-Social Innovations	Governance & Engagement, Education & Capacity Building	Social Cohesion, Well-being	Involves GeoDesign workshops and citizen surveys, promoting inclusive participation in sustainability planning.

Table 11: Madrid LL Initiatives ISO37100 mapping

4.2.3 LL3 - Porto

Innovation	Relevant ISO 37100 Services	Sustainability Features	Relevance
P1-Cool Roof with Bifacial PV	Living & Working Environment, Biodiversity & Ecosystem Services	Preservation & Improvement of Environment, Resilience	The Cool Roof reduces heat absorption, lowering energy demands, while bifacial PV panels enhance renewable energy production.
P2-Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G)	Mobility, Energy Trading & Management	Responsible Resource Use, Resilience	Enables bidirectional energy transfer, improving grid flexibility and integrating renewable energy with EV infrastructure.
P3-Solar-to-Vehicle (S2V)	Mobility, Community Smart Infrastructures	Responsible Resource Use, Resilience	Supports solar-powered EV charging, enhancing local energy autonomy and reducing fossil fuel dependency.
P4-Building-Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV)	Community Smart Infrastructures, Living & Working Environment	Attractiveness, Responsible Resource Use	BIPV panels provide clean energy while being architecturally integrated into building designs.
P5-REC (Renewable Energy Community)	Community Smart Infrastructures, Economy & Sustainable Production	Responsible Resource Use, Social Cohesion	Establishes a local energy-sharing system, allowing collective self-consumption and grid independence.

P6-Second Life Batteries	Safety & Security, Economy & Sustainable Production	Resilience, Responsible Resource Use	Repurposes used EV batteries for stationary energy storage, reducing waste and improving grid reliability.
P7-Smart EV Hub (SEVH)	Mobility, Community Smart Infrastructures	Responsible Resource Use, Resilience	Integrates EV charging with smart energy management, improving energy efficiency and urban transport sustainability.
P8-Phase Change Materials (PCMs)	Living & Working Environment, Economy & Sustainable Production	Preservation & Improvement of Environment, Well-being	PCM technology enhances thermal regulation, reducing heating and cooling energy demand.
P9-Inform Users About Energy Use	Governance & Engagement, Education & Capacity Building	Social Cohesion, Well-being	Provides real-time energy data and recommendations to empower users in making sustainable consumption choices.
P10-Social Innovations & Open Community Lab	Governance & Engagement, Biodiversity & Ecosystem Services	Social Cohesion, Preservation & Improvement of Environment	Creates interactive workshops, biodiversity projects, and citizen engagement programs, fostering a culture of sustainability.

Table 12: Porto LL Initiatives ISO37100 mapping

4.2.1 LL4 - Brussels

Innovation	Relevant ISO 37100 Services	Sustainability Features	Relevance
B1-Cool Roof with Bifacial PV	Living & Working Environment, Biodiversity & Ecosystem Services	Preservation & Improvement of Environment, Resilience	The Cool Roof integrates bifacial PV panels, reducing urban heat islands and improving energy efficiency.
B2-PV Panels	Community Smart Infrastructures, Economy & Sustainable Production	Responsible Resource Use, Resilience	PV panels provide renewable energy generation, supporting energy self-sufficiency and carbon footprint reduction.
B3-Energy Monitoring System	Governance & Engagement, Community Smart Infrastructures	Resilience, Responsible Resource Use	Enables real-time tracking of energy performance, optimizing consumption and efficiency through data analytics.
B4-Social Innovations (IEQ Study)	Governance & Engagement, Health & Care in the Community	Well-being, Social Cohesion	Focuses on Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) monitoring, tracking air quality, thermal comfort, and behavioural patterns in classrooms.

Table 13: Brussels LL Initiatives ISO37100 mapping

4.2.1 LL5 - Aarhus

Innovation	Relevant ISO 37100 Services	Sustainability Features	Relevance
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A1-Flow Batteries	Safety & Security, Community Smart Infrastructures	Resilience, Responsible Resource Use	Energy storage, stabilizing the local grid and reducing reliance on fossil fuels.
A2-Upcycling Renovation Designs	Economy & Sustainable Production, Living & Working Environment	Responsible Resource Use, Preservation & Improvement of Environment	Promotes circular economy principles by integrating recycled and upcycled materials into building renovations.
A3-Human Centred Analysis Tools	Governance & Engagement, Health & Care in the Community	Social Cohesion, Well-being	Uses digital simulations and occupant feedback to optimize building design for user comfort and environmental performance.
A4-Social Innovations	Governance & Engagement, Education & Capacity Building	Social Cohesion, Well-being	GeoDesign workshops, behavioural change initiatives, and public engagement in sustainability.
A99-Biogenic Materials	Biodiversity & Ecosystem Services, Economy & Sustainable Production	Preservation & Improvement of Environment, Responsible Resource Use	Incorporates wood fibre insulation and waste-derived materials, reducing carbon footprint and material waste.

Table 14: Aarhus LL Initiatives ISO37100 mapping

4.2.1 LL6 - Prague

Innovation	Relevant ISO 37100 Services	Sustainability Features	Relevance
PR1-Building-Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV)	Community Smart Infrastructures, Living & Working Environment	Responsible Resource Use, Preservation & Improvement of Environment	Integrates solar panels into the building façade, improving energy efficiency and building aesthetics.
PR2-Green Roof with PV	Biodiversity & Ecosystem Services, Living & Working Environment	Preservation & Improvement of Environment, Resilience	Enhances urban biodiversity, improves stormwater management, and integrates solar PV for energy generation
PR3-Optimal Indoor Air Quality (IAQ)	Health & Care in the Community, Living & Working Environment	Well-being, Resilience	Uses ventilation monitoring and smart sensors to optimize indoor air quality and occupant comfort.
PR4-Digital Twin (DT)	Community Smart Infrastructures, Governance & Engagement	Resilience, Responsible Resource Use	Provides real-time building monitoring, energy optimization, and supports predictive maintenance.
PR5-Virtual Reality (VR)	Education & Capacity Building, Governance & Engagement	Social Cohesion, Well-being	Supports building maintenance training and facility management through immersive digital environments.

Table 15: Aarhus LL Initiatives ISO37100 mapping

5 Conclusions

PROBONO develops practical and innovative solutions for sustainable urban environments towards a standardized, replicable framework for future Green Buildings and Neighbourhood

(GBN) initiatives. It provides a strong foundation for advancing urban sustainability through technology, policy alignment, and stakeholder engagement, ensuring long-term impact beyond the initial implementation phase.

Section 2: To handle the vast complexity of the project, which emanates from the solutions developed and their installation and testing plans in six (6) Living Labs, the Technical Management introduces a PROBONO monitoring methodology which is firstly deployed and used in the Living Labs. The Monitoring Methodology of the Living Labs represents a practical and effective approach that improves on traditional project management by clearly linking strategic goals, technological implementations, and measurable outcomes. Further, it can be scaled to address any type of complexities in managing sustainable urban development projects which in the case of PROBONO appear as the Living Labs designed, constructed and deployed technical solutions. The methodology has been based and extended the ArchiMate 3.2 framework, which was adapted to represent the concepts and to handle the tracking of many exploitable results across the six PROBONO Living Labs which are also presented in this deliverable.

A key achievement is the coordination and sharing of common information and practices across work packages. This is particularly evident in the alignment between WP6 monitoring protocols and WP7 Living Lab activities, where standardized naming conventions ensure the consistent tracking of innovation actions.

This is a consequence, that the methodology is supported by a license free tool for model-based designs, which within creates structures like a Knowledge Graph. Thereby, using the PROBONO extended ArchiMate, it is possible to visually link and map the relationships between innovations, stakeholders, and outcomes, enhancing decision-making and project coordination. Further, Task 7.1 advances the WP6 work relating the monitoring framework, completely subsuming the outputs of it, that categorize technologies based on their impact levels and according to their deployment to the Living Labs. The data-driven approach and the clear visualization of interdependencies which are also navigable, improve communication and increase clarity and transparency as regards the who does what where and why, setting a solid foundation for managing complexity.

Section 3: The analysis of PROBONO's Living Labs highlights the successful implementation of diverse sustainable technologies across different scales and contexts. The flagship Living Labs in Dublin and Madrid showcase large-scale integration of technologies, with Dublin focusing on renewable energy and smart energy management, and Madrid emphasizing district-level

heating and cooling solutions. The smaller scale Living Labs in Porto, Brussels, Aarhus, and Prague demonstrate focused excellence in specific areas, broadening the project's scope.

The monitoring methodology has been particularly effective in maintaining consistent definitions and tracking across work packages. The alignment between WP6's monitoring framework, WP9's exploitation results, and WP7's implementation tracking has enabled reliable evaluation of innovations and their impacts. This has been crucial in managing the complex network of stakeholders, technologies, and outcomes across all Living Labs.

Change management has been a critical factor in the Living Labs' evolution. For example, Porto's shift in mobility solution providers and Brussels' reconsideration of green roof technology implementation demonstrate the flexibility of the Living Labs in addressing challenges while staying aligned with PROBONO's objectives.

Risk assessment across the Living Labs has identified common challenges, such as structural integration issues for deployed technologies, regulatory hurdles for energy storage, and data security concerns for Digital Twin implementations. The varying scales of the Living Labs have provided insights into how these risks differ across contexts, offering valuable lessons for future replication.

The Living Labs monitoring process strength lies in its ability to track developments while maintaining clear connections between innovations, impacts, and stakeholders. Hence, task 7.1 has engaged in a detailed analysis with a clear identification of technology clusters, stakeholder roles, and implementation challenges provides a solid foundation for scaling and replicating successful innovations. Further, the documentation of use cases and data requirements and the import of the Task 5.1 outputs (Deliverable D5.1 about the LL use cases for the Digital Twin) in the model's Knowledge Graph, has expanded the Living Lab knowledge content, and has improved the understanding of each Living Lab's contribution to the broader GBN framework and facilitated knowledge transfer between sites.

Section 4: The clustering and mapping analysis of PROBONO's Living Labs reveals distinct patterns in sustainable urban development approaches, with strong alignment to international standards. Four key clusters have emerged: Energy Performance and Sustainability, Resource Efficiency and Lifecycle Optimization, Scalability and Replicability, and User-Centric Quality Improvements. These clusters highlight the complementary contributions of the Living Labs to the GBN framework. Dublin and Madrid's flagship Living Labs cover all clusters, with Dublin excelling in energy performance and smart management, and Madrid focusing on resource efficiency and lifecycle optimization. The other Living Labs—Porto, Brussels, Aarhus, and

Prague—specialize in areas such as renewable energy, mobility, air quality, and human-centred solutions, creating a diverse range of innovations.

The alignment of these initiatives with the ISO 37100 framework for sustainable communities is particularly noteworthy. The Living Labs collectively address all twelve sustainability initiatives outlined in ISO 37101, from governance and engagement to mobility and smart infrastructure. Each Living Lab contributes to multiple sustainability characteristics—attractiveness, environmental preservation, resilience, responsible resource use, social cohesion, and well-being—demonstrating the holistic nature of PROBONO’s approach.

References

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- D1.4 Strategic Vision KPI Formulation.
- D1.8 GBN Transition Challenges.
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- D5.1 GBN DT Requirements Specifications.
- D6.1 PROBONO Evaluation Framework.
- D6.2 Baseline Evaluation.
- D6.3: Living Labs Monitoring Program and Execution Plan.
- D6.4: Monitoring and Impact Assessment of Construction Activities.
- D7.1: Overall LL Implementation Plan and Management (I).
- D7.2: Overall LL Implementation Plan and Management (II).
- D9.3: Exploitation, Replication, and Sustainability (II).
- D9.7 PROBONO Standardization (I).
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